

“Green” Cross-Linking of PVA-Based Nanostructured Biomaterials: From Eco-Friendly Approaches to Practical Applications

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Abstract

Recently, a growing need for sustainable materials in various industries, especially biomedical, environmental, and packaging applications, has been observed. Poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) is a versatile and widely used polymer, valued for its biocompatibility, water solubility, and easy processing, *e.g.*, forming nanofibers via electrospinning. As a result of cross-linking, PVA turns into a three-dimensional structure – hydrogel with unusual sorption properties and mimicry of biological tissues. However, traditional cross-linking methods often involve toxic chemicals and harsh conditions, which can limit its eco-friendly potential and raise concerns about environmental impact.

"Green" cross-linking approaches, such as the use of natural cross-linkers, freeze-thawing, enzymatic processes, irradiation, heat treatment, or immersion in alcohol, offer an environmentally friendly alternative that aligns with global trends toward sustainability. These methods not only reduce the use of harmful substances but also enhance the biodegradability and safety of the materials. By reviewing and analyzing the latest advancements in "green" PVA cross-linking approaches, this review provides a comprehensive overview of current techniques, their advantages, limitations, and potential applications. The main emphasis is placed on PVA nanostructured forms and applications of PVA-based biomaterials in areas such as wound dressings, drug delivery systems, tissue engineering, biological filters, and biosensors. Moreover, this article will contribute to the broader scientific understanding of how the materials based on PVA can be optimized both in terms of "greener" and safer production, as well as adjusting the final platform properties.

Graphical/Visual Abstract and Caption

"Green" cross-linking methods, such as the use of natural agents, freeze-thawing, enzymatic reactions, irradiation, heat treatment, or stabilization by ethanol, lead to the fabrication of sustainable poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) hydrogel with the desired properties, paving the way for its use in many biomedical applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

Today's world struggles with environmental challenges; Thus, developing eco-friendly materials has become a priority. Cross-linking processes are no exception, with a growing emphasis on sustainable methods that minimize environmental impact. Eco-friendliness refers to materials and practices that are environmentally safe and do not harm our planet. It typically applies to products that promote sustainable living or approaches that protect resources such as water and energy. Additionally, eco-friendly materials aim to minimize or eliminate the release of pollutants into the water, air, and soil ([Bayer, 2020](#)).

Cross-linking is a transformative process that plays a pivotal role in modifying the properties of polymers, enabling their application across diverse scientific and industrial fields. At its core, cross-linking involves the formation of chemical or physical bonds between polymer chains, creating a three-dimensional (3D) network ([Maitra & Shukla, 2014](#)). It can occur both within the same molecule (intramolecular cross-linking) or between different molecules (intermolecular cross-linking) ([Sau et al., 2021](#)). This process significantly alters the physical and chemical characteristics of the material, often enhancing its mechanical strength, thermal stability, and resistance to environmental conditions

[\(Maitra & Shukla, 2014\)](#). Cross-linking is not confined to a specific type of polymer; Wide range of compounds, including hydrophilic [\(Ali et al., 2024; C. Liu et al., 2024\)](#) and hydrophobic [\(Sato et al., 2024; Shao et al., 2024\)](#) polymers, can be cross-linked depending on the desired properties of the final material and its future application. Cross-linking processes typically involve introducing cross-linking agents or applying external stimuli, such as heat, radiation, or pH changes, to facilitate bond formation [\(Maitra & Shukla, 2014\)](#). Cross-linkers, which may include small molecules or larger macromolecules, act as bridges between polymer chains. For example, in the case of poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA), hydroxyl groups along its backbone can react with cross-linking agents to form robust covalent or hydrogen bonds [\(Chousidis, 2024\)](#). Cross-linked polymers undergo significant structural changes. In their non-cross-linked state, polymers generally consist of long, linear, or slightly branched chains. These chains become interconnected upon cross-linking, forming a rigid or semi-rigid three-dimensional network. This change significantly impacts the material's properties, often resulting in reduced solubility and increased stability. The degree of cross-linking, which can range from sparse to dense networks, determines these changes, providing a means to fine-tune the material for specific applications [\(Dyson, 1987; Mathias, 2009\)](#).

Hydrogels represent a particularly fascinating category of cross-linked polymers, notable for their 3D structure and ability to absorb and retain substantial amounts of water [\(Ho et al., 2022\)](#). They can be defined as polymeric gels consisting of two components: an elastic and hydrophilic polymer lattice with loosely cross-linked aliphatic polymer chains and a fluid (water) that fills the interstitial spaces of the lattice. The lattice is used to retain the liquid within the polymer and to give consistency to the gel. In contrast, the liquid prevents the polymeric network from separating as a solid phase (segregation). Therefore, the gel is formed by the interaction between the hydrophilic groups of the polymer and water until a balance is reached, resulting in a phase that can be considered intermediate between a solid and a liquid. As the amount of water retained at equilibrium is variable, the consistency of the gel varies: at low water content, the hydrogel has an almost solid consistency and good mechanical properties while at higher water content it appears as soft gel with poor mechanical properties. Hydrophilic polymers, such as PVA, achieve gel formation, either chemically or physically. Hydrogels

stand out for their unique combination of properties: flexibility, biocompatibility, and a high degree of water content, which closely mimics biological tissues ([Ho et al., 2022](#)). As a result of cross-linking, hydrogels' mechanical strength and elasticity often improve, enabling the material to withstand repeated deformation without losing its structural integrity ([X. Li & Gong, 2024](#)). However, in some cases, this process can reduce the flexibility of the polymer chains, as the network structure restricts their mobility ([Zakrzewska et al., 2025](#)). Thus, the properties of hydrogels can be tailored by cross-linking density ([Guo et al., 2020; Kafaltiya et al., 2024](#)), and a balance between flexibility and strength is crucial for applications where durability and adaptability are needed simultaneously ([X. Li & Gong, 2024](#)). For instance, highly cross-linked hydrogels might prioritize mechanical strength and stability ([Yang Chen et al., 2024; Mellott et al., 2001](#)), making them suitable for load-bearing applications. In contrast, lightly cross-linked hydrogels may favor softness and swelling capacity, ideal for drug delivery or wound healing ([Capitani et al., 2001; Zakrzewska et al., 2025](#)). The properties of hydrogels can be tuned further by incorporating functional groups that provide, for example, conductivity or stimuli-responsiveness ([Kafaltiya et al., 2024; Zakrzewska et al., 2023](#)). Therefore, hydrogels are versatile materials with applications spanning medicine, agriculture, environmental science, and beyond. Their diversity arises from their customizable properties, achieved through careful selection of polymer precursors, cross-linking methods, and additional functionalization ([Guo et al., 2020](#)). For instance, in medicine, PVA hydrogels can serve as scaffolds for tissue engineering ([Xiang et al., 2024](#)), systems for controlled drug delivery ([Fraga et al., 2023](#)), and dressings for wound healing ([Alifah et al., 2024](#)). Their biocompatibility, biodegradability, and ability to mimic extracellular matrices (ECMs) make them ideal for interfacing with biological systems. Moreover, they play a crucial role in environmental science because of their usefulness in water purification ([Zhou et al., 2020](#)) and agriculture ([K. P. et al., 2024](#)). PVA-based hydrogels' water-retention capacity makes them suitable for improving soil moisture content ([Fabian et al., 2024](#)) while functionalized hydrogels can remove pollutants from water sources ([Zhao et al., 2018](#)). In industry, these hydrogels find applications in food packaging ([Sharma et al., 2024](#)), as well as in the production of diapers ([Yuanyuan Chen et al., 2023](#)) and hygiene products, where their ability to absorb large volumes of liquid is invaluable ([Mistry et al., 2023](#)). Furthermore, after the incorporation of stimuli-responsive

components, hydrogels based on PVA are employed in sensors ([Devi et al., 2024](#)) and actuators ([Zheng et al., 2023](#)), exploiting their responsiveness, e.g., to temperature, pH, or light.

Hydrogels' adaptability to various forms, including nanofibers ([Kamoun et al., 2021](#)), films ([W. Gong et al., 2025](#)), beads ([Hao Li et al., 2024](#)), and foams ([Zhen Zhang et al., 2024](#)), further expands their usability.

This diversity underscores their potential to address complex challenges across disciplines, reinforcing their position as a cornerstone of modern material science. Electrospun nanofibrous hydrogels deserve special attention. Electrospinning is a technique that uses high voltage to eject a precursor solution from a syringe equipped with a metal needle ([Ji et al., 2024](#)). Because the needle and the grounded collector differ in potential, the ejected solution begins to stretch and settles in the form of continuous nano-sized fibers on the collector surface ([Yarin et al., 2001](#)). Nanofibrous hydrogels combine the features of both materials – the large specific surface area of nanofibers, which improves adsorption and interactions with the environment, and the water retention capacity of the hydrogel matrix, which is conducive to biomedical and environmental applications. This synergistic combination is extremely difficult to obtain in other materials.

Eco-friendly cross-linking of PVA involves using non-toxic, biodegradable agents or leveraging physical cross-linking techniques that eliminate the need for harmful chemicals. For instance, natural compounds such as citric acid (CA) derived from citrus fruits ([Zakrzewska et al., 2025](#)) can act as cross-linking agents, offering a “greener” alternative to synthetic chemicals. Moreover, natural compounds derived from vegetable oils or animal fats such as glycerol, can function as bridge molecules, connecting PVA chains into bundles by forming numerous hydrogen bonds, van der Waals forces, and hydrophobic interactions, thereby forming a gel network ([Kosik-Kozioł et al., 2024](#)). Similarly, physical methods such as freeze-thaw (F-T) cycles ([Sa'adon et al., 2019](#)) or UV irradiation ([Bayrak et al., 2024](#)) can achieve cross-linking without introducing hazardous substances. The benefits of adopting eco-friendly, so-called “green” approaches extend beyond environmental preservation. These methods often enhance the biocompatibility and safety of the resulting materials, making them more suitable for applications in healthcare and personal care products. Additionally, the integration of renewable

resources in hydrogel synthesis aligns with the principles of circular economy, promoting sustainable development.

Traditional chemical cross-linkers often raise concerns related to toxicity and environmental impact, highlighting the need for eco-friendly alternatives. By examining the latest advancements in the "green" PVA cross-linking methods, this review offers a comprehensive overview of current techniques, highlighting their benefits, limitations, and potential applications. Furthermore, it contributes to the broader scientific understanding of optimizing PVA-based biomaterials for safer and more sustainable nanoscale production, while also refining the final system properties to meet emerging industrial and biomedical needs.

2. POLY(VINYL ALCOHOL) – A CHEMICAL OVERVIEW

Poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA, CAS no. 9002-89-5) is the most important commercially available water-soluble synthetic polymer in terms of quantities produced annually; In 2016, its production in the USA and Pacific Asia was about 753 kilotons ([Aslam et al., 2018](#)). It is not produced directly from vinyl alcohol since this monomer is unstable as it tends to tautomerize to acetaldehyde.

PVA can be efficiently prepared from poly(vinyl ethers) or poly(vinyl esters) but, at an industrial level, is almost exclusively produced by transesterification of poly(vinyl acetate) (PVAc).

During its radical polymerization, PVAc tends to give chain transfers with the acetate group, generating relatively low molecular weights, which can be reflected in the corresponding PVA mass ($M_w = 22.000\text{--}100.000\text{ g mol}^{-1}$) ([Nawaz & Hümmelgen, 2019](#)). The latter also has good content in Head-to-Tail (HT) dyads and is generally crystalline, although its precursor polymer, PVAc, is completely amorphous. This is because –OH groups, present in PVA structure, are small and allow the polymer chains to come close together to form that maximum-packing structure and density typical of polymer crystals; Indeed, inter- and intrachain hydrogen bonds keep this compact structure well-established and stable. The formation of this high crystallinity makes the fully hydrolyzed PVA not soluble in water (only partially and at 85 °C), while the PVA containing 12–15% acetate groups is well soluble even in cold water.

The residual content of acetyl groups can be varied, mainly depending on the base concentration, the kind of solvent, the reaction time, and temperature. Fully hydrolyzed commercial PVA has 98–99 mol% of acetate functional groups converted to –OH, intermediate grade: 93–97 mol%, and partially hydrolyzed: 85–90 mol%. PVA is slightly water-soluble when hydrolysis is less than 70% and PVA polymers hydrolyzed between 70 and 90% are polyampholytic, thus able to lower the surface tension of water. This results in a U-shaped solubility curve, where water solubility peaks at intermediate hydrolysis (70–90%) and decreases at both lower (<70%) and higher (>98%) degrees due to hydrophobicity and crystallinity, respectively. The degree of hydrolysis affects not only solubility but also several key thermal and structural properties. An increasing degree of hydrolysis increases tensile strength (up to 67–110 MPa) and water/solvent resistance, while partial hydrolysis gives enhanced flexibility and solubility to PVA hydrogels ([Tamaki & Chujo, 1998](#)). With higher hydrolysis, the polymer also demonstrates an increase in glass transition temperature (T_g) and a reduction in free volume, as evidenced by smaller cavity radii ([Fong et al., 2018](#)). This relationship highlights how increased hydroxyl content enhances chain rigidity, elevating T_g and reducing free volume, ultimately creating a denser, more stable polymer matrix (**Figure 1a**). Partially hydrolyzed PVA has a melting point of 180–190 °C while the corresponding value for the fully hydrolyzed polymer rises to 230 °C, thanks to the possibility to form more hydrogen bonds in the matrix.

The free-radical polymerization of vinyl acetate to PVAc is usually initiated by thermal initiators (benzoyl peroxide, azobisisobutyronitrile, cumyl hydroperoxide) or by UV-initiators (benzoin) in methanol. This first step is followed by chain propagation and then by termination, either by chain combination or disproportionation ([Tesoro, 1986](#)). During polymerization chain transfer, reinitiation and solvent transfer reactions can occur, raising the polydispersity index (usually around 2). The monomer conversion is not complete and the residual portion of unreacted vinyl acetate has to be recycled. A similar way to prepare PVAc is by emulsion polymerization, using water-soluble thermal or redox initiators (like ammonium persulfate), a surfactant and water as a reaction medium. At the end of the polymerization, the emulsion is broken using aluminum sulfate, and the polymer is recovered by filtration.

The second step involves the transesterification of PVAc with methanol using a small amount of base (or acid) to catalyze the exchange reaction between methanol and PVAc, giving PVA and methyl acetate. Methanol is used to solubilize PVAc and to control the reaction temperature. A direct hydrolysis of PVAc in water by an acid or a base is a less-performing reaction, being poly(vinyl acetate) practically insoluble in water. PVA in water acts as a surfactant, reducing the surface tension of the solution thanks to the stronger interactions of macromolecules segment with water and allowing its chains to be localized in the interface between air and water ([H. Lee et al., 2012](#)).

In partially hydrolyzed PVA, the distribution of acetate and hydroxyl groups is not random along the polymeric backbone, but the different units are arranged following a block structure. Little amounts of acetone, methyl acetate, or benzene can be added to the methanol in order to increase the amount of blocks in the final polymer ([Nagara et al., 2001](#)). PVA is relatively safe when administered orally (oral acute toxicity LD50 in rats and mice are 20 g kg⁻¹ and 14.7 g kg⁻¹, respectively) ([Kelly et al., 2003](#)) since it is scarcely absorbed by the gastrointestinal tract and easily eliminated from the body. PVA coatings and films are employed as binding and coating agents in the food industry when moisture and oxygen/aroma barrier properties are required.

By reacting the polymer with aldehydes, including formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, glutaraldehyde, and other monoaldehydes, PVA can be chemically cross-linked through the formation of acetalic bridges, giving PVA hydrogels. Another way to cross-link PVA chains, avoiding the use of harmful reagents, is physical cross-linking: PVA at high molecular weight (50.000–100.000 g mol⁻¹), high hydrolysis degree (>98%) and relatively high concentration in water (10–20% w/w) can be cryogelled using F-T conditions ([Muppalaneni, 2013](#)). Recently, a novel strategy has emerged utilizing thermally activated persulfates for free radical-induced cross-linking of PVA ([F. Li et al., 2021](#)). This method stabilizes PVA by cross-linking through the generation of carbon-based radicals and simultaneously degrades coexisting organic pollutants, such as textile dyes, in solution (**Figure 1b**). Activated at elevated persulfate concentrations and temperatures, this approach enhances cross-linking through oxidation of hydroxyl groups while reducing PVA's water absorption capacity, confirming it as a dual-purpose solution in applications where polymer stabilization and pollutant removal are both essential.

The density of cross-linking also affects the stability and strength of a PVA hydrogel. It is clear that the toughness and mechanical properties of the gel will increase with the degree of cross-linking, but it is important not to exceed a limit value in order to preserve the elasticity of the polymer cross-section. In fact, if the cross-linking degree is too high, the gel does not form, causing the system to be very rigid, while if it is too low, the gel will dissolve in water. Moreover, cross-linking of PVA can also be an effective solution to reduce its high hygroscopicity since interchain linkages reduce the density of hydroxyl groups by converting them to less polar ether groups. As already mentioned, the gelation of PVA can occur using physical cross-linking, by means of a series of F-T cycles of polymer aqueous solutions ([Lambertini et al., 2024](#)). During thermal cycles, PVA chains intermingle with themselves and can cross-link, exploiting electrostatic interactions, ionic interactions, hydrogen bonding, and chain entanglements ([M. Yang et al., 2023](#)), giving a porous network structure with an enhanced mechanical strength. Moreover, PVA hydrogels stabilized through physical cross-linking can exhibit unique thermo-reversible properties, since the interchain hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic interactions form lamellar junction knots that maintain the gel network (**Figure 1c**). Pedersen *et al.* showed that external heat can disrupt this structure, enabling the hydrogel to undergo liquefaction under controlled conditions ([Pedersen et al., 2020](#)). Photothermal dyes or nanoparticles have been incorporated within these hydrogels, allowing for rapid, localized heating and triggered disintegration when exposed to near-infrared (NIR) light. This adaptation facilitates the on-demand release of entrapped molecules, which is suitable for targeted drug delivery and biotechnology. PVA hydrogels can also be strengthened using borax (sodium tetraborate decahydrate), which forms borate ester bonds acting as cross-linking points. This is the mechanism for the development of “Slime” ([McLaughlin et al., 1997](#)), a toy introduced in 1976 and manufactured by Mattel.

Thanks to their biocompatibility, drug compatibility, water solubility, film-forming ability, and good mechanical and swelling properties, PVA hydrogels have been successfully employed for biomedical applications ([Nagarkar & Patel, 2019](#)) (surgical threads, drug delivery systems, implantable medical devices and contact lenses), membranes for fuel cells, chemosensors, and optical devices ([Moulay, 2015](#)). Moreover, PVA is the only vinyl polymer that can be biodegraded by some ubiquitous microorganisms

like *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, and *Pseudomonas*, which use the polymer as a source of carbon and energy (Ben Halima, 2016). In a recent study, endophytic fungi have been identified as promising candidates for PVA biodegradation, with *Penicillium brevicompactum* OVR-5 showing significant efficacy by achieving up to 81% degradation within 10 days under optimal conditions (Mohamed et al., 2021). This biodegradation process relies on the catalytic activity of fungal enzymes, such as lipase, manganese peroxidase, and laccase, which bind to PVA surfaces and initiate breakdown through oxidation of hydroxyl groups and cleavage of carbon-carbon bonds (Figure 1d). Through these reactions, PVA is transformed into smaller compounds, such as acetic acid and hydroxyl fatty acids, which can enter the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle. The study is promising as it shows the potential of fungal-based treatments as environmentally friendly solutions for PVA waste management.

Figure 1. Key characteristics of PVA: hydrolysis effects, cross-linking, hydrogel formation, and biodegradability. a) Influence of PVA's degree of hydrolysis on its glass transition temperature and free volume characteristics. As the degree of hydrolysis increases, T_g rises while cavity radius decreases, indicating reduced free volume and increased chain rigidity. Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license ([Fong et al., 2018](#)), Copyright 2018, The Authors. b) Overview of PVA's cross-linking capabilities. Illustrated here is a thermally activated persulfate mechanism, generating sulfate and hydroxyl radicals, achieving “two birds with one stone” by simultaneously free radical cross-linking and degrading coexisting pollutants. Reproduced with permission ([F. Li et al., 2021](#)), Copyright 2020, Elsevier B.V. c) Schematic of the PVA hydrogel network stabilized by physical cross-linking, where interchain hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions form thermo-reversible junction knots. Reproduced with permission ([Pedersen et al., 2020](#)). Copyright 2020, American Chemical Society. d) Proposed PVA biodegradation pathway highlighting the initial cleavage of PVA by extracellular dehydrogenase or oxidase, followed by further breakdown into acetic acid via hydrolase or aldolase reactions (left). SEM images showing pristine PVA (top) and PVA with reduced fiber diameter after 10 days (bottom), indicating significant polymer biodegradation over time (right). Reproduced with permission ([Mohamed et al., 2021](#)), Copyright 2021, The Authors, under exclusive license to Springer Nature B.V.

3. PVA PROCESSING

3.1 Macroscopic structures

Due to their favorable structural, mechanical, and chemical properties, cross-linked PVA-based materials have been developed in a variety of macroscopic structures, such as films, hydrogels, and microspheres. These materials, alone or in combination with other substances, have been used in various fields, including biomedical, industrial, and environmental applications.

The good water solubility of PVA makes wet processing, such as solvent casting, a popular technique for producing PVA films. Despite being energy-intensive and time-consuming, it is often preferred over thermal processing due to PVA's low thermal stability. Processing factors that mostly influence the film microstructure, morphology, and properties are gelation temperature and relative humidity ([Sasaki](#)

[& Suzuki, 2016](#)), as they determine the solvent drying speed and, consequently, the growth of microcrystallites ([Otsuka *et al.*, 2012](#)). Furthermore, microporous PVA films can be prepared by various phase separation methods, as discussed in a recent review by Sapalidis ([Sapalidis, 2020](#)). Recently, “greener” approaches have been developed to overcome some critical aspects of traditional processing and obtain complex structures with enhanced properties. For instance, in the work published by M'barki *et al.*, a new environmentally friendly method for preparing porous membranes was explored ([M'barki *et al.*, 2014](#)). The process combines thermally induced phase separation (TIPS) and cross-linking of PVA in water, operating at relatively low temperatures (60 °C) to save energy and reduce costs. The membrane's morphology and porosity were controlled by varying the phase separation, the cross-linking degree, and the drying process parameters, such as relative humidity. The structures obtained showed interconnected porosity and hydrophilic behavior, with possible applications as anti-fouling materials ([M'barki *et al.*, 2014](#)).

Solvent casting is a versatile technique for producing PVA films due to the ease of incorporating various cross-linkers into the casting solution and functional additives. Suganthi *et al.* successfully employed this method to create cross-linked PVA films for food packaging applications using organic acids (OA) as cross-linkers ([Suganthi *et al.*, 2020](#)). Microstructural, physicochemical, and antimicrobial characterization of the various materials obtained confirmed the effectiveness of solvent casting in forming these films with enhanced antibacterial properties ([Suganthi *et al.*, 2020](#)). Sau *et al.* investigated the effects of heat treatment on cross-linked PVA films by comparing the structural, morphological, spectroscopic, and mechanical properties of heat-treated films with those of untreated PVA ([Sau *et al.*, 2021](#)). Their findings revealed that thermal treatment increases the crystallinity of cross-linked PVA, consequently modulating the material's optical and mechanical properties ([Sau *et al.*, 2021](#)). Magnetically responsive PVA materials were prepared by solvent casting embedding Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles with potential use in drug delivery systems, biosensors, and tissue engineering devices ([Huang *et al.*, 2021](#)). These materials exhibit tunable surface wettability, which can be increased by applying an external magnetic field and subsequently reversed by switching the field off, thus regulating protein

sorption and release. In another work, lignin nanospheres were distributed in a PVA matrix to obtain a film with enhanced mechanical properties and UV-shielding features ([Huang et al., 2021](#)).

PVA films find widespread applications in various fields, including medical devices, industrial processes, water treatment, fuel cells, and gas separation ([Vatanpour et al., 2023](#)). Blending, cross-linking, and copolymerization are frequently employed to enhance membrane stability ([Thakur et al., 2019](#)).

3D porous PVA structures, like foams and aerogels, are commonly obtained by traditional techniques, such as freeze-drying and gas foaming. Freeze-drying comprises three stages: freezing, primary drying, and secondary drying. Freezing, conducted below the solvent's triple point, facilitates subsequent sublimation during primary drying, where 95% of the solvent is removed. This low-speed step is the most critical as it determines the final material structure. During the secondary drying, residual unfrozen solvent molecules evaporate ([Fereshteh, 2018](#)). Gas foaming, a technique often used to produce highly porous and interconnected materials, relies on the nucleation and growth of gas bubbles within the polymer matrix. These bubbles can be generated *in situ* through chemical reactions or by introducing inert gases into the polymer phase at various pressures. The process typically involves three steps: polymer/gas solution formation, bubble nucleation, and pores growth ([Bianchi et al., 2024](#)). Common blowing agents in conventional gas foaming include carbon dioxide, pentane, argon, nitrogen, and air ([Costantini & Barbeta, 2018](#)). Supercritical CO₂ (sc-CO₂) is often employed for gas foaming, offering a “greener”, more cost-effective, and more controllable alternative to traditional methods ([Reverchon et al., 2008](#)). The method consists of dissolving sc-CO₂ in the solid polymer at high pressure, generating a low-viscosity mixture. Subsequently, the depressurization decreases sc-CO₂ solubility in the polymer and leads to the phase transition of CO₂ from supercritical to gas. CO₂ bubble nucleation occurs, and nuclei growth generates pores within the polymer. Concomitantly, the viscosity of the polymer/sc-CO₂ mixture increases till all the gas has escaped from the polymer, leaving behind a solid structure with “locked-in” pores ([Barry et al., 2006](#)). In the work of Lin *et al.*, a porous PVA/citric acid (CA) foam was fabricated using sc-CO₂ (**Figure 2a(left)**) ([Lin et al., 2024](#)). The authors investigated the effects of processing parameters (PVA/CA contents, temperature, pressure, and saturation time) on the resulting material's

properties. The foaming process facilitated the formation of PVA foams with densities that could be modulated by changing the cross-linking degree of PVA and CA and the processing conditions (**Figure 2a(right)**). Furthermore, the presence of sc-CO₂ led to the formation of small amounts of carbonic acid, which promoted cross-linking between polymer chains. This approach thus provided a “green” method for fabricating PVA foams with thermal insulation properties ([Lin et al., 2024](#)).

Microfluidics has emerged as a powerful technique for fabricating size-controlled PVA-based microspheres ([Luo et al., 2020](#); [J. Wang et al., 2019](#); [S.H. Yang et al., 2022](#)). For example, Yang *et al.* developed a novel microfluidic strategy to fabricate PVA microspheres for embolization using a solution of PVA and boric agent (dispersed phase) and n-octanol as a continuous phase (**Figure 2b(left)**) ([S.H. Yang et al., 2022](#)). The emulsion droplets size and morphology (**Figure 2b(right)**) were controlled by adjusting the flow rates and the dimensions of the microfluidic device, while elasticity was tuned by controlling the ratio of PVA and boric acid ([S.H. Yang et al., 2022](#)). 3D printing technologies have been widely used to construct three-dimensional materials of nearly every shape for diverse applications. Because a PVA solution itself does not possess yield stress, its printability is possible only with the addition of other molecules. For instance, in the work by Sargur Ranganath *et al.*, PVA was blended with non-chemically modified, micro-fibrillated cellulose (MFC) to create a printable ink for direct ink writing (DIW) ([Sargur Ranganath et al., 2022](#)). Their study investigated various PVA/MFC compositions and examined the influence of DIW parameters on print uniformity. The overall ink characteristics were evaluated through rheological measurements, enabling the selection of the optimal composition for 3D printing ([Sargur Ranganath et al., 2022](#)). Interpenetrating polymer networks (IPNs) are among the most common structures developed by 3D printing. These networks are characterized by the combination of a rigid frame, typically originated by non-reversible chemical bonds, and a weaker network based on reversible physical bonds. Caprioli *et al.* developed a self-healing PVA/acrylic acid hydrogel via vat photopolymerization, produced using a commercial Digital Light Processing printer ([Caprioli et al., 2021](#)). The properties of the final materials were tailored by balancing the cross-linking ratio and water content of the hydrogel. The work thus provided a valid approach to fabricating self-healing hydrogel objects with complex structures for applications in diverse fields such

as robotics, medical devices, and energy storage ([Caprioli et al., 2021](#)). The melting process of PVA in 3D printing through fused deposition modeling is currently widely proposed in pharmaceutical industries for the manufacturing of solid preparation for drug delivery ([Surini et al., 2023](#)). Cotabarren *et al.* investigated the effects of printing parameters (such as material flow rate and printing speed) and optimized the process to allow the production of capsular devices in a single manufacturing step ([Cotabarren & Gallo, 2020](#)). The development of complex structures, from scaffolds to wearable devices, makes 3D printing a promising technique to fabricate PVA-based materials with unique properties and a wide range of applications.

3.2 Nanofibrous materials

Nanofibrous structures of PVA are fabricated using the electrospinning technique. This method uses electrostatic forces to uniaxially stretch a viscoelastic jet derived from a polymer solution or melt, resulting in the formation of continuous fibers with diameters typically ranging from 50 nm to 2 μ m ([Xue et al., 2019](#)). The versatility of the technique allows the engineering of individual fibers through the blend, emulsion, or coaxial electrospinning, facilitating the production of multicomponent fibers that can be loaded with nanoparticles, drugs, or bioactive agents. Thereby it offers a wide range of material properties and functionalities ([Gualandi et al., 2014](#)). Furthermore, the surface of nanofibers can be functionalized with bioactive molecules or coatings through post-processing treatments, including plasma treatments, wet chemical methods, physical vapor deposition, or graft polymerization ([Sagitha et al., 2018](#)). Depending on the specific electrospinning setup, fibers can be deposited as non-woven mats with random, aligned, or custom orientations, or assembled into three-dimensional structures and yarns ([Yujie Chen et al., 2022](#)). Electrospun fibers can be exploited for a range of applications, including air filtration ([Lu et al., 2021](#)), sensors ([Babu et al., 2023](#)), catalytic systems ([S. Li et al., 2019](#)), water treatment ([T M et al., 2021](#)), energy harvesting/conversion/storage ([Q. Liu et al., 2017](#)), structural composites ([G. Wang et al., 2017](#)), and biomedical applications ([G. Yang et al., 2018](#)).

PVA nanofibers have been fabricated using PVA with varying degrees of hydrolysis ([Park et al., 2010](#)) and solubilized in different solvents. Water is commonly employed due to its non-toxicity, environmental

sustainability, and ability to effectively dissolve PVA. However, binary solvent systems have also been investigated, including water/ethanol, water/acetic acid ([Mahmud et al., 2018](#)), and water/dimethyl sulfoxide ([Gupta et al., 2016](#)). These mixed solvent systems can influence polymer chain interactions and solvent evaporation rates, enabling the production of nanofibers with different morphological characteristics in terms of diameter, surface porosity, and geometry of the fiber section.

In numerous studies, PVA was blended with other polymers to improve the electrospinnability of the resulting solutions and tailor their functional properties for specific applications. Chitosan (CS), in particular, is frequently combined with PVA due to its intrinsic antibacterial activity, making the blend highly suitable for biomedical uses. For instance, Abdelgawad *et al.* developed electrospun PVA/CS 60/40 nanofibers embedded with silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) and further cross-linked using glutaraldehyde vapors ([Abdelgawad et al., 2014](#)). The synergistic action of CS antimicrobial properties and the biocidal effect of AgNPs resulted in enhanced antibacterial performance, making the fibers ideal for wound dressing applications ([Abdelgawad et al., 2014](#)). More recently, Maleki *et al.* developed PVA/CS 80/20 scaffolds incorporating ginger and thyme herbal extracts, cross-linked with glutaraldehyde vapor ([Maleki et al., 2024](#)). The material exhibited antioxidant activity and effectively inhibited the growth of both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. *In vivo* tests demonstrated the scaffold's ability to promote rapid wound closure and skin regeneration ([Maleki et al., 2024](#)).

Beyond antibacterial effects, the ability of CS to chelate heavy metal ions was exploited by Habiba *et al.* ([Habiba et al., 2017](#)). Researchers fabricated PVA/CS 50/50 electrospun fibers loaded with zeolites, a porous material known as a metal ion absorber. After cross-linking in glutaraldehyde vapors, this composite membrane effectively adsorbed moderate concentrations of Cr^{6+} , Fe^{3+} , and Ni^{2+} ions, highlighting its potential for use in water purification and heavy metal removal ([Habiba et al., 2017](#)).

The incorporation of 1.5% w/w of UiO-66 metal-organic framework (MOF), synthesized over thermally oxidized nanodiamond, into PVA/CS 75/25 nanofibers was proposed for the treatment of dye-contaminated water after cross-linking in glutaraldehyde vapors ([Ahmadijokani et al., 2023](#)). These materials effectively removed cationic methylene blue and anionic Congo red (carcinogenic) dyes,

demonstrating an 80% increase in maximum dye adsorption capacity compared to unfilled PVA/CS ([Ahmadijokani et al., 2023](#)).

Food packaging and preservation is a growing field of application of PVA-based electrospun materials. Recently, Cheng C. *et al.* prepared PVA/CS membranes containing different amounts of 1,8-cineole, the major component of Eucalyptus essential oil ([C. Cheng et al., 2023](#)). 1,8-cineole was stabilized by a previous encapsulation into hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin through the co-precipitation method. The obtained materials displayed excellent antibacterial and antioxidant activity. They can inhibit microbial growth and fruit browning and maintain the freshness of strawberry fruit by extending their shelf life to 6 days at room temperature (RT) ([C. Cheng et al., 2023](#)). Jiang L. *et al.* blended PVA with pullulan to produce electrospun fibers incorporating bayberry pomace anthocyanins for smart food packaging ([L. Jiang et al., 2024](#)). The materials exhibited pH sensitivity, displaying a significant color change across different pH levels. The electrospun nanofiber films appeared red at pH 2, pink at pH 3, retained their pink color up to pH 11, and shifted to dark blue at pH 12. Additionally, they responded to ammonia gas exposure, changing from pink to green after just 1 min of exposure. These properties enable the electrospun mats to monitor white shrimp quality in real-time by effectively indicating freshness during storage at 4 °C, as evidenced by color transitions from pink to greyish/purple to green ([L. Jiang et al., 2024](#)).

Sodium alginate (SA) is another polysaccharide commonly combined with PVA to fabricate electrospun membranes for various applications. In the work by Jiang *et al.*, electrospun fibers composed of PVA and SA were cross-linked by thermal treatment and with CaCl_2 and surface-decorated with iron-based MOF (Fe-MOF) ([X. Jiang et al., 2023](#)). Fe-MOF is an efficient photocatalyst due to its exceptional photo-Fenton activity, which induces the generation of reactive oxygen species under visible light irradiation (**Figure 2c(top)**). The incorporation of SA in the fibers significantly contributed to the *in situ* growth of Fe-MOF crystals, attributed to the polysaccharide's strong chelating ability toward metal ions. The resulting composite membranes exhibited remarkable performance in oil/water emulsion separation thanks to their superhydrophilicity, which enabled efficient water permeation while repelling oil droplets (**Figure 2c(bottom-left)**). Furthermore, the membranes demonstrated rapid degradation of organic dyes under visible light exposure (**Figure 2c(bottom-right)**), making them highly promising for wastewater

treatment applications ([X. Jiang et al., 2023](#)). Das *et al.* blended PVA with SA to develop urea-loaded PVA/SA 80/20 fibers as a controlled-release fertilizer system ([Das et al., 2023](#)). The fibers, cross-linked with CaCl₂, displayed a sustained urea release profile for >21 days in water and >30 days in soil and a water retention capacity of up to 16 days, highlighting its potential for use in agriculture and horticulture ([Das et al., 2023](#)). In the study by Golafshan *et al.*, PVA/SA 80/20 fibers, cross-linked through thermal treatment and CaCl₂ were loaded with different concentrations of graphene to develop materials for engineering nerve tissue ([Golafshan et al., 2017](#)). The influence of graphene content on the mechanical, structural, chemical, electrical, and biological properties of the fibrous scaffolds was investigated. A concentration of 1% w/w of graphene was enough to improve fiber toughness and overcome the percolation threshold, resulting in the formation of a broad electrically conductive path and better promoting the adhesion of PC12 cells ([Golafshan et al., 2017](#)).

Blending PVA with collagen has been proposed as a valuable option for tissue regeneration. In a recent work by Liu *et al.*, PVA was blended with type I collagen to prepare electrospun membranes ([Y. Liu et al., 2024](#)). After a process of mineralization, they were enriched with aragonite nanocrystals (**Figure 2d(left)**). The resulting fibers stimulated the adhesion and the growth of bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells (BMSCs) after 12 and 21 days, as well as their osteogenic differentiation (**Figure 2d(right)**), revealing its potential for biomedical applications in hard tissue engineering ([Y. Liu et al., 2024](#)).

Regardless of the PVA processing method, it is important to note that the presence of voids within the final material can significantly influence its mechanical strength, swelling capacity, and barrier properties. Voids may act as stress concentrators, reducing the material's toughness, while also altering the diffusion of liquids and gases through the polymer structure ([Liu et al., 2022](#); [Lim et al., 2024](#)). Therefore, controlling the formation of voids during PVA processing and post-processing treatments (e.g., cross-linking) is crucial for achieving the desired properties of PVA-based materials.

Figure 2. Illustrative representation of different processing techniques used for PVA-based materials fabrication. a) Scheme of the fabrication process of PVA foams by sc-CO₂ foaming (left); The influence of saturation time on the final properties of the resulting porous structure in terms of morphology and thermal conductivity (right). Reproduced with permission ([Lin et al., 2024](#)), Copyright 2024, Elsevier Ltd. b) Schematic illustration of the microfluidic-based strategy, showing the microfluidic device for the PVA microspheres preparation and the cross-linking reaction inside the template droplet (left); SEM images and EDS analysis of PVA microspheres (right). Reproduced with permission ([S.H. Yang et al., 2022](#)), Copyright 2022, American Chemical Society. c) Schematic synthesis of MIL-88A(Fe)@PVA-SA nanofiber membrane and corresponding SEM micrograph (top); Photographs and optical microscopy images showing the separation tests of oil-in-water emulsions (bottom-left); Variation in the UV-Vis spectra of methylene blue (MB) and reactive red 24 (RR) with time in the presence of MIL-88A(Fe)@PVA-SA membrane, representing its photo-Fenton catalytic activity (bottom-right). Reproduced with permission ([X. Jiang et al., 2023](#)), Copyright 2023, Elsevier B.V. d) Schematic fabrication of PVA/Col–CaCO₃ via electrospinning together with SEM and TEM images of the mineralized nanofibers (left); Results of Alizarin Red S (ARS) test, proving the highest degree of mineralization and successful osteogenic differentiation in PVA/Col–CaCO₃ fibers (right). Reproduced with permission ([Y. Liu et al., 2024](#)), Copyright 2025, The Royal Society of Chemistry.

4. CROSS-LINKING PROCESS

The cross-linking process for PVA involves bonding the polymer chains either chemically or physically. This creates a network structure that enhances the material's properties, including increased mechanical strength, improved chemical resistance, and reduced water solubility.

Chemical cross-linking involves forming covalent bonds between PVA molecules to create a cross-linked network, thereby enhancing PVA's mechanical strength and water resistance ([Truong et al., 2017](#); [J.Y. Wu et al., 2021](#)). This process typically uses a cross-linking agent to form bonds between polymer chains. A common chemical cross-linking agent for PVA is glutaraldehyde, which reacts with the hydroxyl groups on PVA chains to form stable acetal linkages. The process generally involves mixing

an aqueous solution of PVA with glutaraldehyde under acidic conditions, where the acid acts as a catalyst to accelerate the cross-linking reaction ([Figueiredo et al., 2009](#)).

Physical cross-linking involves the formation of physical bonds such as hydrogen bonds or ionic interactions ([Adelnia et al., 2022](#)). While not as stable or strong as chemical cross-linking, it can improve the material's resistance to water and its mechanical properties. One way to achieve physical cross-linking of PVA is through repeated freezing and thawing cycles ([Adelnia et al., 2022](#)). During freezing, PVA chains crystallize and form physical cross-links through hydrogen bonding. When thawed, some of these cross-links are retained, enhancing the structural integrity of the polymer network. Unlike chemical cross-linking, this method does not require external chemical agents, making it particularly useful in biomedical applications where non-toxic, biocompatible materials are preferred. However, physically cross-linked PVA is generally less stable in water and can degrade over time compared to chemically cross-linked one.

4.1 Importance and impact of cross-linking on the PVA properties

Due to the hydrophilic hydroxyl groups in the side chain of PVA, it tends to swell or even dissolve in humid or water environments, limiting its applications. Therefore, cross-linking is necessary to enhance PVA's physical, chemical, and mechanical properties, making it suitable for various uses. The cross-linking process is instrumental in creating new materials with broad functionality.

At the micro level, cross-linking restricts the mobility of polymer chains, affecting crystal structure, crystal size distribution, and degree of crystallinity. Generally, this process reduces crystallinity and increases the amorphous region. In PVA, cross-linking occurs through hydroxyl groups, reducing their density for hydrogen bonding with water and decreasing the polymer's water absorption capacity. Additionally, cross-linking restricts chain mobility, controlling the swelling phenomenon and the free volume available for water molecules inside the polymer matrix.

Various studies have explored different cross-linking approaches to achieve specific properties for target applications, including improved mechanical strength ([Sau et al., 2021](#)), enhanced thermal stability ([Dai et al., 2018](#)), reduced solubility in water ([B. Liu et al., 2022](#); [Nguyen & Lee, 2022](#)), controlled swelling in

hydrogel state ([Adelnia et al., 2022](#); [Stauffer & Peppast, 1992](#)), improved chemical resistance ([B. Liu et al., 2022](#)), or introduce tailored functionality ([Nguyen & Lee, 2022](#)).

For many applications, the mechanical strength of PVA is crucial. For example, as a packaging material, it must have good strength to ensure durability during handling and resistance to tearing ([Oun et al., 2022](#)). In one study ([Sau et al., 2021](#)), the tensile strength of PVA film was optimized by heating at 140 °C for 40 min, producing the strongest film and demonstrating that heat treatment is an effective method for physical cross-linking without additional cross-linkers.

To improve the thermal stability of PVA, chemical cross-linking forms stronger covalent bonds, enhancing heat resistance. Other approaches include incorporating nanoparticles such as silica ([Pingan et al., 2017](#)), graphene oxides ([W. Chen et al., 2018](#)), or metal-organic frameworks ([Dai et al., 2018](#)).

Reducing the water solubility of PVA is often necessary. In one study ([Nguyen & Lee, 2022](#)), adding alkyl ketene dimer at 10% w/w to PVA and curing at 120 °C for 1 h improved water resistance and water vapor barrier properties. This improvement was attributed to the reaction between alkyl ketene dimer and PVA, confirmed using Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy.

PVA cross-linking greatly improves the material's durability, mechanical strength, thermal stability, and resistance to water and chemicals. This process also allows for customized functionalities. As a result of cross-linking, PVA can be used in a broader range of applications, including packaging, medical devices, textiles, paper, and fluid filtration membranes. The choice of cross-linking method depends on the desired properties of the final product, acceptable toxicity levels, and the cost and feasibility of the process.

4.2 Chemical methods

Chemical cross-linking involves the formation of covalent bonds between PVA molecules, creating a cross-linked network that enhances both the mechanical strength and water resistance of PVA; This process usually requires a cross-linking agent ([Gautam et al., 2022](#)). A few common cross-linking agents for PVA include glutaraldehyde ([Zhaodi Zhang et al., 2020](#)), citric acid ([Truong et al., 2017](#)), and boric acid

[\(Hong et al., 2021\)](#). These compounds react with the hydroxyl groups in PVA, forming stable cross-linked structures.

Figure 4 illustrates PVA covalent bonding using three above-mentioned chemical cross-linkers. For glutaraldehyde, the acetalization reaction forms acetal bridges between PVA and GA (**Figure 3a**). In contrast, citric acid reacts with PVA through esterification, where the carboxyl groups of citric acid react with the hydroxyl groups of PVA to form ester bonds (**Figure 3b**). In the method involving boric acid, NaOH is used for the breakage of intermolecular hydrogen bonds in PVA. Then, the obtained O-Na can easily react with $B(OH)_4^-$, resulting in the formation of a hydrogel network (**Figure 3c**).

Other less commonly used cross-linkers for PVA include various types of carboxylic acids [\(Gautam et al., 2022\)](#), blocked di-isocyanates [\(J.Y. Wu et al., 2021\)](#), epoxy cross-linking agent [\(Y. Zhang et al., 2022\)](#), humic acid [\(TorresFiguerola et al., 2023\)](#), tannic acid [\(W. Zhang et al., 2023\)](#), and alkyl ketene dimer [\(Nguyen & Lee, 2022\)](#).

Alkyl ketene dimer is a common paper sizing agent in the paper industry as an additive to achieve a reduction in water solubility and an increase in hydrophobicity via contact angle measurement. Nguyen and Lee found the optimum alkyl ketene dimer level to be 10% w/w, and β -ketoester linkages between AKD and PVA were confirmed using FT-IR analysis [\(Nguyen & Lee, 2022\)](#).

Some conventional chemical cross-linkers are harmful or toxic, posing risks to living organisms and the environment. For instance, glutaraldehyde is known to be toxic to cells, limiting its use in biomedical applications. Prolonged or repeated exposure to glutaraldehyde can cause respiratory issues and skin irritation in humans. Therefore, researchers working with PVA as a biomaterial and in other fields seek safer and more environmentally friendly cross-linking alternatives.

Figure 3. Representative methods of PVA chemical cross-linking. a) Spraying with glutaraldehyde solution: Scheme of hydrogel preparation (top) and the mechanism of an acetalization reaction catalyzed by an acid, resulting in the formation of acetal bridges between PVA and glutaraldehyde molecules (bottom). Reproduced with permission ([Zhaodi Zhang et al., 2020](#)), Copyright 2020, The Polymer Society. b) Addition of citric acid: SEM images showing the effect of the cross-linker concentration on the nanofibrous hydrogel's stability in water (top) and the mechanism of temperature-mediated esterification reaction between the hydroxyl groups (–OH) of PVA and the carboxyl groups (–COOH) of CA (bottom). Reproduced with permission ([Truong et al., 2017](#)), Copyright 2017, WILEY-VCH

Verlag GmbH & Co. c) Use of boric acid: Initially, NaOH disrupts the intermolecular hydrogen bonds in PVA generating reactive O–Na groups. Then, these groups interact with $B(OH)_4^-$ leading to the development of a hydrogel network. Reproduced with permission ([Hong et al., 2021](#)), Copyright 2021, Wiley Periodicals LLC.

4.3 Physical methods

Physical cross-linking involves forming physical bonds such as hydrogen bonds or ionic interactions. Although these bonds are not as stable or strong as chemical cross-linking, they can still enhance the material's water resistance and mechanical properties.

Freeze-thawing is a well-established technique for producing PVA hydrogels and recently was reviewed by Adelnia *et al.* ([Adelnia et al., 2022](#)). F-T consists of two main processes: the freezing step is performed on the precursor solution at a temperature below 0 °C, then the temperature is increased during the thawing step up to room temperature. By controlling the number and duration of F-T cycles, it is possible to control the ice crystallization process (freezing) and the formation of an ordered structure (thawing) to modulate hydrogel properties. The F-T cross-linking mechanism is schematically shown in **Figure 4a** ([Waresindo et al., 2023](#)). The properties derived from the process depend on several parameters, mainly PVA concentration and duration, as well as the number of F-T cycles, albeit the presence of additives ([Hübner et al., 2023](#); [Heng Li et al., 2020](#)) can also affect the final structure. An early study demonstrated the effectiveness of the F-T approach for physical cross-linking of PVA using a 15% w/w PVA solution ([Stauffer & Peppast, 1992](#)). The optimal conditions for producing the strongest gels involved freezing a 15% w/w PVA solution at -20 °C for 24 h, followed by thawing at 23 °C for 24 h, repeated for 5 cycles. In their study, Ye *et al.* evaluated the effect of PVA molecular weight, surfactant concentration, foaming time, and stirring speed on morphological, structural, and, consequently, mechanical properties. More specifically, it was observed that increasing the stirring time, surfactant concentration, and stirring rate can enhance the structure porosity. Moreover, high molecular weight promoted the formation of interconnected pores ([Ye et al., 2014](#)). Similarly, Masri *et al.* investigated the influence of PVA concentration, solvent ratios, and the number of freeze-thaw cycles on the

mechanical behavior of the resulting PVA hydrogels. Their findings demonstrated that the initial PVA concentration was the primary factor influencing the material's viscoelastic properties. Although less significant, the number of freeze-thaw cycles and solvent ratios also played a role. By carefully adjusting these parameters, it is possible to tailor the hydrogel properties to specific applications ([Masri et al., 2017](#); [Oliveira et al., 2019](#)).

Similarly, physical cross-linking of PVA can also be achieved by the addition of propanol to remove water from cast films to achieve hydrogen bonding ([E.R. S. Kenawy et al., 2023](#)). In this study, curcumin-loaded PVA/aloe vera hydrogel membranes were prepared via physical cross-linking for topical wound healing application. After the formation of the membrane via casting solution and RT drying, membranes were soaked in propanol for 6 h to obtain physical cross-links. The mechanism of the process is schematically shown in **Figure 4b** ([E.R. S. Kenawy et al., 2023](#)).

Physical cross-links can be also achieved via heat treatment. This approach is described in the study of [Sau et al.](#), where PVA films were prepared using a solution casting method ([Sau et al., 2021](#)). As shown by the structures in **Figure 4c**, heat treatment can lead to both intermolecular and intramolecular cross-linking. The bonds formed between the hydroxyl groups on the PVA backbone are known as hydrogen bonds.

Another approach of cross-linking without the addition of a cross-linking agent is PVA irradiation ([Cieśla & Abramowska, 2021](#)). This involves using high-energy radiation (such as gamma rays or electron beams). The radiation has sufficient energy to break chemical bonds within the PVA molecules to generate free radicals; Free radicals on different PVA chains will react with each other to form covalent bonds, linking the polymer chains together. Radiation cross-linking is advantageous because it does not require additional chemical agents, making it a cleaner process. It is particularly useful in applications where residual chemicals are undesirable, such as in biomedical devices.

Figure 4. Representative methods of PVA physical cross-linking. a) Freeze-thaw cycles: Mechanism of ice crystal creation and gel formation (top); Influence of the polymer molecular weight on the hydrogel microstructure (center); Influence of the freezing and thawing cycles duration on the hydrogel morphological characteristics (bottom). Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license ([Waresindo et al., 2023](#)), Copyright 2023, The Authors. b) Propanol addition: PVA cross-linking through its dehydration under the influence of alcohol. Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license ([E.R. S. Kenawy et al., 2023](#)), Copyright 2022, The Authors. c) Heat treatment: Probable PVA cross-linking mechanism with the use of relatively high

temperature. Cross-linking results in the formation of both intramolecular and intermolecular bonds.

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4.4 "Green" cross-linking of PVA-based biomaterials: a nanostructure-oriented perspective

"Green" PVA cross-linking methods include the use of natural cross-linkers, freeze-thaw method, exposure to the irradiation, enzymatic reactions, heat treatment, and use of alcohol in order to stabilize polymer structure. These approaches can also be combined in various configurations; The goal is to sustainably produce hydrogels with high functionality and durability, which at the same time fit into the idea of a circular economy.

4.4.1 Natural cross-linking agents

One of the best-known and studied natural PVA cross-linking agents is the aforementioned citric acid. The cross-linking process using CA usually requires thermal treatment, which causes dehydration of the carboxyl groups of the acid and, thus, their activation. Then, an esterification reaction occurs between the –COOH groups of citric acid and the –OH groups of PVA, and the resulting ester bonds are responsible for the formation of a stable three-dimensional network. For instance, Jeong and Oh fabricated anti-acne face masks by electrospinning a solution of PVA and citric acid in which zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnONPs) were dispersed ([Jeong & Oh, 2022](#)). The nanofibers were then heated at 160 °C for 1 h under vacuum, inducing a cross-linking reaction. The PVA/ZnONPs composite nanofibers became insoluble in water, they had a high swelling ratio and showed antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Cutibacterium acnes*. The latter is a Gram-positive bacterium that causes acne vulgaris ([Jeong & Oh, 2022](#)). Kharazmi *et al.* prepared another composite nanofibers by incorporating β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) and copper oxide nanoparticles (CuONPs), synthesized from mint leaves, into the PVA/CA system ([Kharazmi et al., 2023](#)). The nanofibers were exposed to a temperature of 150 °C for 3 h under atmospheric conditions to initiate a cross-linking reaction. Due to the presence of β -CD and CuONPs rich in functional groups, the nanofibers showed high extraction efficiency of three tested antidepressant drugs, being effective adsorbents in the pipette-tip micro solid-phase extraction

(SPE) procedure. Imipramine, citalopram, and clozapine were simultaneously extracted from biological fluids for further quantification using gas chromatography. It has been shown that after 60 cycles, the repeatability of microextraction is maintained, and the process has a lower limit of detection (LOD), better accuracy, higher recovery rate, and shorter extraction time compared to other reported SPE methods ([Kharazmi et al., 2023](#)). Taking inspiration from the environmentally safe and effective approach to cross-linking PVA with CA, Zakrzewska *et al.* developed a novel method involving pure, freshly squeezed lemon juice as a natural source of citric acid ([Zakrzewska et al., 2025](#)). Using the electrospinning technique, nanofibers were prepared from a precursor solution in which PVA was dissolved in 100% lemon juice. Acidic pH and additional low-temperature treatment (60 °C for 7 days) enabled the esterification reaction to occur, and as a result, a water-insoluble material with gel content over 71% was obtained. The spectrophotometric analysis confirmed the chemical interaction between PVA and lemon juice, as well as the associated higher cross-linking efficiency compared to samples without the addition of the fruit component. As a result, the PVA/lemon juice system had increased stability over time and improved mechanical properties manifested by an increased Young's modulus compared to as spun nanofibers and much higher elasticity compared to control PVA samples not enriched with lemon ingredient. The nanoplatform showed potential for use in wound healing dressings due to its biocompatibility, antioxidant properties, and antibacterial effect against *Staphylococcus aureus* (**Figure 5a**) ([Zakrzewska et al., 2025](#)).

Dialdehyde polysaccharides (DAPs) are "green" alternatives to low molecular weight organic dialdehydes such as glutaraldehyde. Although glutaraldehyde is widely used for PVA cross-linking, it is also known to be toxic and, therefore, unsafe from the biomedical applications' perspective ([Muchová et al., 2022](#); [W. Wang et al., 2023](#)). DAPs can be prepared by regioselective oxidation of polysaccharides by introducing a pair of reactive aldehyde groups into the system ([Muchová et al., 2022](#); [Q. Wang et al., 2024](#)). The number of cross-linking sites of the DAP macromolecule can be easily controlled by changing its oxidation state as the cross-linking process involves the formation of hemiacetal bonds between the reactive –CHO groups of DAP and the –OH groups of PVA ([Muchová et al., 2022](#); [Münster et al., 2018](#)). Muchová *et al.* investigated the properties of PVA hydrogels, such as swelling, network

parameters, viscoelastic properties, porosity, and cytotoxicity, depending on the structural differences of the DAP cross-linker ([Muchová et al., 2022](#)). The results revealed that with the decrease in the number of –CHO groups, the swelling ability and porosity of the hydrogel increase, and its elasticity decreases. Moreover, the linear structure or branching of the DAP chain also results in the formation of PVA hydrogels with different characteristics. The use of linear polysaccharides such as 2,3-dialdehyde cellulose (DAC) or 2,3-dialdehyde hyaluronate (DAH) is advantageous because the obtained materials are less dependent on the concentration and heat treatment, while branched polysaccharides can bring both positive (2,3-dialdehyde dextran, DXA) and negative (2,3-dialdehyde dextrin, DXI) effects. Moreover, larger cross-linking nano-assemblies are able to bind even relatively distant matrix chains at low concentrations, while smaller ones perform well at higher concentrations, where they form a dense network of relatively small chemically cross-linked domains complemented by physical interaction between PVA chains (**Figure 5b**). The researchers emphasized that DAC is a highly effective hydrogel cross-linker at both high and low concentrations, although obtained materials have low porosity and slightly higher cytotoxicity compared to other analyzed DAP. On the other hand, DXA and DAH are characterized by the lowest cytotoxicity, with DXA being the most optimal among tested ones for biomaterials fabrication ([Muchová et al., 2022](#)).

4.4.2 Freeze-thaw method

A combined cross-linking approach for PVA-based hydrogels was used by Jiang *et al.* ([C. Jiang et al., 2024](#)). The researchers developed a two-step strategy to obtain the synergistic effect of both physical and chemical cross-links in one material. The first step involved reinforcing PVA hydrogels with bacterial cellulose (BC) nanofibers while making them stimuli-responsive. Both entities have hydrophilic characters due to their multihydroxyl backbones; Therefore, they physically connect via hydrogen bonds. In this step, two freeze-thaw cycles of the aqueous PVA/BC precursor solution were used to form PVA microcrystallites. The prepared system was further freeze-dried, and the formed aerogel was soaked in borax solution (RT) in order to obtain a PVA/BC hydrogel with double cross-links. Hence, BC nanofibers could not only nucleate the crystallization of PVA in the first step but, in

the second stage of the process, also create chemical bonds of boronate esters with the polymer chain, *i.e.*, covalent networks. The entire procedure is schematically shown in **Figure 5c**. The synergistic effect of both types of bonds improved the mechanical performance of the hydrogels, which achieved a nearly 4.4-fold increase in tensile strength and a 10-fold increase in toughness compared to pure PVA. In the case of PVA hydrogel containing only physical bonds, the increase was 1.9-fold and 2.8-fold, respectively. Moreover, the obtained system had ionic conductivity due to the ionization and hydrolysis of borax involved in the formation of bonds. Elevated temperature improves the conductivity of the hydrogel due to the increased level of ionization, and the sensitivity to temperature in the range corresponding to the human body exceeds the value of commercial products by 4 times. Moreover, the system is stretchable with a moderate level of elongation. Thus, it can be used in multimodal flexible temperature and strain sensors, including those for biomedical applications ([C. Jiang et al., 2024](#)). A slightly different approach to freeze-thaw cross-linking was presented by Zhang *et al.* ([Q. Zhang et al., 2022](#)). This work describes the preparation of a composite material based on PVA with the addition of aloe polysaccharide (AP) and honey. AP was extracted from *Aloe barbadensis* and then added to a PVA solution containing honey. To the prepared solution, borax was added, and two F-T cycles were performed to form a three-dimensional hydrogel structure. This approach takes advantage of the presence of many hydroxyl groups in AP, PVA, and honey, which can react with borax to form the aforementioned borate ester bonds. The F-T method was used to produce a microcrystalline region that could enhance the mechanical properties of the hydroxyl groups. The conducted studies have shown that the composite hydrogel with 10% w/v honey content consists of over 70% water and has high moisturizing properties within 72 h. Its 3D structure is porous, and its good mechanical properties and ability to kill *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Candida albicans* bacteria make it an ideal candidate for use in multifunctional wound healing dressings. *In vitro* studies have confirmed the biocompatibility of the hydrogel, and *in vivo* tests have shown an effect accelerating the healing of infected wounds in rats by reducing inflammation, supporting collagen deposition, generating growth factors, and inducing angiogenesis. In the **Figure 5d**, it can be seen that the combination of the F-T approach with the incorporation of a new substance acting as a cross-linker into the system results in

the formation of interpenetrating polymer and nanocomposite networks. This additionally facilitates the adjustment of the final hydrogel properties depending on its intended application ([Q. Zhang et al., 2022](#)). However, it should be emphasized that borax is a naturally occurring mineral, non-toxic in low concentrations, biodegradable, and relatively safe to use. In contrast, in its higher concentrations, chronic exposure may have harmful effects.

The F-T method alone is also widely used as it allows the creation of ultrapure hydrogels with outstanding properties (**Figure 6a**) ([Adelnia et al., 2022](#)). In 1975, Peppas proved that repeated freeze-thaw cycles of PVA solutions result in phase separation and crystallization to form a gel ([Peppas, 1975](#)). The freezing step causes PVA chains to become entrapped between ice crystals due to phase separation. During thawing, the gel network forms as the ice crystals transform into the pores of the hydrogels. With an increasing number of cycles, more chains are incorporated into the PVA crystallites, enhancing the gel's strength. Important factors of gelation are the number of cycles and their duration, temperature, as well as the molecular weight and degree of the polymer hydrolysis ([Adelnia et al., 2022](#)). For instance, Sa'adon *et al.* prepared a bilayer transdermal patch using the electrospinning technique and cross-linking of the PVA-based system by the F-T method ([Sa'adon et al., 2019](#)). The first layer consisted of electrospun nanofiber, while the second one was PVA film. The researchers evaluated the effect of the number of freeze-thaw cycles on the obtained hydrogel morphology and its swelling ability. The results of the study showed that increasing the number of F-T cycles from 3 to 5 caused a decrease in the swelling capacity of the patch (from 66 to 33%), however, the presence of large surface area nanofibers has a positive effect on the swelling of the whole construct. Since the PVA nanofibers have a large surface area, they could still absorb a large volume of water despite the denser cross-linking. Moreover, the morphology studies of the two-layer system confirmed the correlation between the cryogel and the nanofiber membrane, which did not dissolve completely after the precursor solution layer was poured onto it before the F-T process. It was claimed that the obtained system could be used as a transdermal patch to deliver therapeutic agents at a constant rate through the surface of human skin ([Sa'adon et al., 2019](#)).

Figure 5. "Green" approaches to PVA cross-linking and their effect on hydrogel properties: natural cross-linking agents and combined strategies. a) Biocompatible nanofibrous hydrogel electrospun from PVA/fresh lemon juice solution, possesses antioxidant and antibacterial properties, improved mechanical properties and thermal stability, making it suitable for use in biomedical applications. Reproduced with permission ([Zakrzewska et al., 2025](#)), Copyright 2025, American Chemical Society. b) Schematic illustration of the binding modes characteristic of various dialdehyde polysaccharides cross-linking agents. Purple dots represent the number of cross-linking points per molecule, reflecting the relative ratio of aldehyde ($-CHO$) groups. The unified size of the PVA matrix corresponds to the same polymer concentration. Reproduced with permission ([Muchová et al., 2022](#)), Copyright 2021, Elsevier Ltd. c) Scheme of preparation and double cross-linking of poly(vinyl alcohol)/bacterial cellulose hydrogel. The first stage involved freeze-thaw cycles resulting in physical interaction (hydrogen bonds) between PVA and BC. In the second step, the aerogel was immersed in a borax solution to form covalent bonds, thereby achieving dual cross-linking responsible for outstanding mechanical properties of the obtained

hydrogel. Reproduced with permission ([C. Jiang et al., 2024](#)), Copyright 2024, Elsevier B.V. d) Scheme of fabrication of a natural PVA-based hydrogel wound dressing enriched with aloe polysaccharide and honey. Cross-linking by borax addition combined with a freeze-thawing method resulted in hydrogel with improved mechanical properties, antibacterial activity, and biocompatibility, as well as the ability to accelerate the healing of infected wounds in rats. Reproduced with permission ([Q. Zhang et al., 2022](#)), Copyright 2022, Elsevier B.V.

4.4.3 Enzymatic reactions

In addition to chemical and physical cross-linking of polymers, there are also biological cross-linking methods that have not been widely reported. Recently, this approach has developed, and the use of enzymes—bioactive macromolecules ensuring biological safety and biocompatibility—has increased ([Z. Li et al., 2023](#)). The first hydrogel cross-linked with glutamine transaminase in the enzymatic reaction was described by Sperinde *et al.* in 1997 ([Sperinde & Griffith, 1997](#)). In the following years, the cross-linking properties of enzymes from the polyphenol oxidase and peroxidase groups were discovered, which are currently also used for PVA stabilization ([Z. Li et al., 2023](#)). For example, Niu *et al.* produced semi-IPN hydrogels consisting of PVA and silk fibroin (SF) synthesized from raw silk fibers ([Niu et al., 2019](#)). As shown in **Figure 6b (top)**, PVA/SF systems were subjected to enzymatic cross-linking using horseradish peroxidase (HRP) and H_2O_2 . In this case, the cross-linking mechanism is based on the formation of tyrosine radicals of SF macromers under the influence of HRP and gelation in the presence of H_2O_2 . The resulting tyrosine radicals react with each other to form covalent bonds between silk fibroin chains, while hydrogen bonds are formed between the $-OH$ groups of the polymer and the $-NH-$ groups of SF. The latter strengthens the structure of the PVA/SF semi-IPN hydrogel network. Hydrogel extracts were subjected to *in vitro* cell studies, demonstrating their biocompatibility ([Niu et al., 2019](#)).

Another enzyme commonly used in biological cross-linking processes is microbial transglutaminase (mTGase). In short, transglutaminases catalyze the cross-linking of proteins such as collagen and gelatin. Moreover, some of these enzymes are crucial during epidermis wound healing, taking part in

the process of keratinocyte differentiation ([Eckert et al., 2005](#)). However, there are examples in the literature of PVA-based systems containing gelatin that took advantage of mTGase capability to cross-link protein components. For instance, Sengor *et al.*, for the first time, reported successful fabrication of core-shell PVA-gelatin nanofibers cross-linked *in situ* with mTGase ([Sengor et al., 2020](#)). For the coaxial electrospinning, aqueous PVA solution and aqueous gelatin/mTGase solutions with variable enzyme concentrations were used. mTGase could not be added to the system after the fabrication process, as it requires an aqueous environment for enzymatic activity, which would destroy the nanofibrous structure of the as spun material. Gelatin/mTGase solutions were found to be spinnable if their viscosity was lower than 9.5 centipoise. Furthermore, a mTGase concentration of 0.5% w/w provided solution with viscosity allowing electrospinning for 240 min ([Sengor et al., 2020](#)). Another approach to the preparation of gelatin-PVA hydrogels was used by Corona-Escalera *et al.* ([CoronaEscalera et al., 2022](#)). The researchers mixed aqueous solutions of gelatin and PVA, pasteurized it, and finally loaded with *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* cells. Then, an aqueous solution of mTGase was added to the probiotic-loaded solution and poured into a cylindrical vessel for cross-linking. The mechanism of this reaction is schematically shown in **Figure 6b (bottom)**. Enzymatic stabilization of the gelatin-PVA (Gel-PVA) system was aimed at protecting cell viability during further freeze-drying and under simulated gastrointestinal conditions. SEM analysis showed a macroporous, densely cross-linked structure containing bacteria with interlocking polymer networks providing integrity. FT-IR and ¹H-NMR analyses revealed chemical modifications between PVA and gelatin due to cross-linking. Indeed, the studies performed showed over 90% loading efficiency of probiotics into the Gel-PVA system and their 91% survival during freeze-drying after entrapment in the hydrogel matrix. Moreover, under gastric conditions the survival of bacteria was over 94%, as the environment did not cause the hydrogel to disintegrate. It dissolved only in intestinal fluid containing bile salts releasing the *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*, thus, proving potential to be used in oral systems for probiotic delivery ([CoronaEscalera et al., 2022](#)).

4.4.4 Irradiation

Another “green” method of PVA-based materials cross-linking is the use of radiation, including microwave, ultraviolet (UV), or gamma (γ) radiation. The mechanism of this cross-linking is based on processes initiated by high energy provided by radiation, *i.e.*, the disintegration of chemical bonds in PVA chains and ionization of water with the formation of free radicals. The resulting radicals can react with each other, creating new bonds between PVA chains, or react with water and oxygen molecules present in the system, leading to the formation of additional cross-links or structural modifications. However, it should be remembered that radiation can cause both cross-linking and chain breaking, depending on the radiation power, crystallite size, and environmental factors ([Charlesby, 1953](#)). Afzal *et al.* investigated the effect of microwave radiation on the thermal properties and crystallinity of PVA/graphene nanocomposites ([Afzal et al., 2020](#)). Nanocomposites with different contents of graphene nanoparticles were prepared by solution casting method and then cross-linking using a household microwave oven with a power of 200 W for 5, 10, and 15 min. As a result of these studies, it turned out that nanocomposites with graphene content above 1% ignite after 5 s of irradiation due to too high concentration of a substance characterized by very high thermal conductivity. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) revealed that the incorporation of graphene into the PVA matrix decreases the crystallinity and thermal stability of the polymer because this addition restricts chain movement and causes synergistic instability between both components of the nanocomposite; However, the crystallization rate increased. Moreover, 5 min irradiation improves the crystallinity and thermal stability of the PVA/graphene nanocomposite due to better dispersion of nanoparticles in the matrix, whereas longer heating results in degradation of the polymer chains and the crystal structure of nanoparticles ([Afzal et al., 2020](#)). Another example is the development of hybrid electrospun N-maleoyl functional chitosan (MCS)/PVA nanofibers capable of reductant-responsiveness by Chen and Huang ([C.K. Chen & Huang, 2016](#)). In this work, for the first time, MCS/PVA system was stabilized through UV irradiation with the addition of allyl disulfide as a cross-linker (**Figure 6c**). Both chitosan (CS) and PVA are biocompatible polymers widely used in wound dressing fabrication. At first, the researchers synthesized an MCS through the amidation reaction of

CS precursors. Then, MCS and PVA were mixed, electrospun, and subjected to the cross-linking process. The MCS/PVA nanofibers cross-linked with allyl disulfide and UV radiation have exhibited excellent water stability, desirable swelling characteristics, non-toxic properties, and triggered drug release functionality in the presence of biocompatible reductant. Thus, their significant potential for clinical use as active wound dressings was emphasized. Additionally, the attachment and spreading of L929 fibroblast cells on the final construct were clearly visualized through SEM ([C.K. Chen & Huang, 2016](#)). Another example of cross-linking of PVA-based nanomaterial using UV radiation for wound healing applications was described in the work of Bayrak *et al.* ([Bayrak *et al.*, 2024](#)). The researchers fabricated PVA/melanin nanoparticles (MNP) blend nanofibers and core-shell nanofibrous system, which were widely tested for potential use in dressings accelerating wound healing. To produce the nanofiber blend, a 10% w/w aqueous solution of PVA and a 5% w/w aqueous solution of MNP, previously extracted from commercially available squid (*Sepia officinalis*) ink sacs, were mixed in a ratio of 7:3. The same concentrations of solutions were used to fabricate the hybrid nanofibers, with MNP as the core and PVA as the shell. After electrospinning, the materials were irradiated with LEDs emitting UV-A radiation (395–400 nm) for 30, 60, and 300 s. Morphological analysis revealed that the diameter of the nanofibers decreased after irradiation, and attenuated total reflectance (ATR)-FT-IR analysis confirmed the systems' cross-linking. Moreover, the core-shell nanoplateform cross-linked for 30 s by UV-A irradiation proved to be a viable alternative for antibacterial dressings, which was attributed to the photocatalytic activity of melanin nanoparticles. Under these conditions, MNP-PVA blended nanofibers and core-shell hybrid nanofibers eliminated *Escherichia coli* bacteria by 41.6% and 32%, respectively. Additionally, core-shell nanofibers promoted wound closure by 99.2% at 24 h after irradiation ([Bayrak *et al.*, 2024](#)). Therapy using UV radiation is known as photodynamic therapy (PDT) and has recently become an alternative to traditional treatments. PDT takes advantage of UV light capability to eliminate viruses, fungi, mycoplasmas, and bacteria, including multidrug-resistant ones ([Bayrak *et al.*, 2024; Cutler & Zimmerman, 2011](#)).

Various intended applications of biomaterials require adaptation of their properties, including ensuring appropriate mechanical resistance. To increase the mechanical strength of PVA-based hydrogels, the

polymer can be combined with other substances. Chen *et al.* developed doubly cross-linked PVA/cellulose nanofiber (CNF) composite hydrogels for use in artificial joint cartilage ([Yang Chen et al., 2024](#)). In the first stage, materials with different CNF content (0.0–0.9% w/w) were chemically cross-linked using a γ^{60} source with an absorbed dose of 30 kGy. Then, physical cross-linking was applied by annealing at 80 °C and rehydration (**Figure 6d**). After exposure of the materials to gamma radiation, an increase in gel content, tensile strength, and elongation at break, as well as lower water absorption capacity were observed with an increase in CNF concentration. The annealing stage of PVA/CNF hydrogels resulted in an increase in cross-linking density and a change in their micromorphology. It was found that a composite containing 0.6% CNF, which after exposure to gamma radiation was stretched by 30% and, in this form, subjected to a temperature of 80 °C for 6 h, shows great improvement compared to a pure PVA hydrogel. An increase in crystallinity was observed from 19.9% to 25.8%, and tensile strength increased from 65.5 kPa to 21.2 MPa, with an elastic modulus of 4.2 MPa. An increase in CNF concentration also caused a decrease in the friction coefficient of the composites. Significant improvement in the mechanical properties of the hydrogels and excellent lubrication properties make the obtained systems potential candidates for applications in artificial joint cartilage ([Yang Chen et al., 2024](#)).

4.4.5 Heat treatment

Cross-linking of PVA using temperature involves physical processes and is based on the formation of hydrogen bonds and crystalline areas in the polymer. High temperature increases the kinetic energy of PVA chains, allowing them to reorganize and orient themselves into more ordered structures. Hydrogen bonds are then formed between the hydroxyl groups of adjacent chains, and areas that form regular crystalline structures act as "nodal points", strengthening the polymer network. Mahmud *et al.* prepared electrospun PVA nanofibers loaded with curcumin, which were then cross-linked by two methods: temperature treatment (80-160 °C for 2 h) and UV radiation (40 W for 30 min, 1 h, and 2 h) ([Mahmud et al., 2020](#)). The aim was to obtain stable nanoplateforms capable of controlled release of curcumin, which possesses antibacterial activity. SEM analysis did not allow for observing curcumin in the fibers,

but its incorporation into the system was confirmed by XRD data. However, based on SEM images, it could be stated that the presence of curcumin in the fibers causes a reduction in their diameter, thermal treatment results in thickening of the fibers compared to as spun material, while UV cross-linking does not affect their morphology. There were also no significant changes in mechanical or degradation properties as a result of any of the tested approaches. Most importantly, both heat-treated and UV-irradiated samples showed a reduced release rate of curcumin from the nanofibers even by 20% (160 °C for 2 h) and 9% (40 W for 2 h), respectively. As their swelling ability reached over 300% and their ability to kill both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria was confirmed, the PVA/curcumin-loaded hydrogels proved to be good candidates for wound dressing applications ([Mahmud et al., 2020](#)). Another dressing supporting wound healing was presented by Eakwaropas et al. ([Eakwaropas et al., 2020](#)). Scientists developed a new generation of PVA-based nanofibrous hydrogels with the addition of *Ipomoea pes-caprae* (IPC) leaf extract. IPC has numerous biologically important properties such as antimicrobial, antioxidant, analgesic, and anti-inflammatory effects. In this work, PVA nanofibers were prepared by electrospinning a 10% w/w aqueous polymer solution. Then, the nanofibers were subjected to heat treatment at 180 °C for 0.5, 1, 2, or 4 h for cross-linking and loaded with IPC extract prepared before from fresh leaves. The loading process involved immersion of hydrogels in the solution of IPC extract for 24 h. The study showed that the swelling capacity and durability were significantly improved compared to the conventional bulk PVA/IPC hydrogel cross-linked by the F-T method, which was prepared in this study for comparative purposes. Moreover, the developed hydrogel had a higher loading capacity and released the active compound much faster compared to the conventional material at 2 and 4 h. Its ability to kill *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria was also confirmed, which could be attributed to the presence of adsorbed IPC extract. On this basis, the potential of IPC-extract loaded nanofibrous PVA hydrogel for use in the healing of infected wounds as a new generation dressing was established ([Eakwaropas et al., 2020](#)). However, the possibilities of using PVA-based hydrogels are much broader. Zhu et al. developed ultralight PVA nanofiber/starch aerogels (NFA-S) with significantly improved mechanical properties ([J. Zhu et al., 2020](#)). The fabrication process involved electrospinning followed by freeze-drying and simple thermal cross-linking (at 80, 120,

and 200 °C for 2 h). A small quantity of gelatinized starch was incorporated into the system to serve as a nanoglue, efficiently binding the 3D porous nanofiber wall networks and, thus, improving the mechanical properties of the NFA-S. Importantly, heat treatment additionally influenced the mechanical resistance of the material, which was finally able to endure loads up to 1000 times its own weight. The aerogel considered optimal was characterized by 99.1% porosity, which provided thermal insulation properties and low thermal conductivity. Such a micro-nano structure, combined with good mechanical properties and 95.3% efficiency of filtering particles smaller than 300 nm (pressure drop 44.1 Pa), makes NFA-S valuable in many areas such as air filters, personal wearable protection (face masks, ultralight thermal clothing), and electronics (smart wearable sensors). NFA-S multifunctionality is additionally demonstrated by the change in its affinity for water after cross-linking. The non-cross-linked material was hydrophilic, while thermal treatment gave it hydrophobic properties and opened the way to the application for oil-water separation ([J. Zhu et al., 2020](#)).

4.4.6 Alcohol-based stabilization

Cross-linking of PVA with monohydric alcohols involves the creation of physical interactions both between polymer chains and between the polymer and the alcohol. More importantly, alcohols such as methanol and ethanol, being solvents with lower polarity compared to water, reduce the hydration of PVA. This leads to the approximation of the polymer chains and the intensification of hydrogen interactions between the –OH groups. Heating the material in the presence of alcohol additionally promotes the reorganization of the polymer chains. Zakrzewska *et al.* fabricated semi-IPN hydrogel where PVA nanofibers were cross-linked and water-soluble polythiophene derivative (poly[3-(potassium-5-butanoate)thiophene-2,5-diyl], P3KBT) was trapped inside the network remaining in its linear molecular form ([Zakrzewska et al., 2023](#)). In this work, two selected cross-linking methods were used, *i.e.*, heat treatment (at 160 °C for 2 h), named method H, and immersion in ethanol (for 24 h) combined with heating (at 160 °C for 20 min), named method E. Then, the obtained materials were extensively characterized in order to understand the influence of the cross-linking approach on their final properties. The studies revealed the high efficiency of both cross-linking methods as the obtained

hydrogels became insoluble in water at RT and 39 °C, which is close to the human body temperature. This finding was additionally supported by FT-IR analysis. Morphological analysis using FE-SEM allowed to observe an increase in the diameter of nanofibers after stabilization compared to as spun nanofibers, which was attributed to the formation of complex network structures. The cross-linking density was assessed to be higher in the case of H samples, which also had better mechanical properties manifested by lower stiffness and higher flexibility. The lower cross-linking density of E samples resulted in the release of some P3KBT amount after immersion in water. On the other hand, E samples were characterized by a higher swelling ratio and had higher electrical conductivity resulting from the presence of semiconducting P3KBT. Interestingly, the presence of this polymer also provided photo-responsiveness to all nanofibrous hydrogels. Temperature changes under the influence of simulated solar radiation were higher the higher the concentration of P3KBT. All systems were also biocompatible. The collected data proved a strong correlation between cross-linking approaches and hydrogel properties; Therefore, cross-linking methods should be used properly depending on the desired application of the developed material ([Zakrzewska et al., 2023](#)). The same cross-linking method, meaning immersing nanofibers in ethanol and then their thermal treatment, was previously used by Gao et al. ([Gao et al., 2020](#)). Researchers prepared electrospun PVA nanofibers loaded with epidermal growth factor (EGF) modified with 3,4-dihydroxyphenethylamine (DOPA). After electrospinning, PVA nanofibers were immersed in ethanol for 24 h, dried in the desiccator, and then placed in an oven at 160 °C for 20 min. EGF was incorporated into a nanofibrous matrix using a bioorthogonal approach (combining recombinant DNA technology with tyrosinase treatment) and then transformed into DOPA-EGF, where DOPA was bound to the active site of EGF at its terminal. The main action of EGF is to facilitate the migration and proliferation of epidermal cells (keratinocytes) and connective tissue (fibroblasts), as well as the formation of granulation, thus facilitating the wound healing process. At the same time, DOPA improves the specific adsorption and covalent binding of EGF to the polymer. Performed analyses showed that cross-linking improved the water resistance and crystallinity of the fibers. *In vitro* cell studies indicated that PVA/DOPA-EGF hydrogel promotes the proliferation of NIH-3T3 cells, which are mouse embryo tissue fibroblasts. The proliferation showed ~1.41-fold and ~1.47-fold increase,

respectively, compared to the PVA nanofibers with physically adsorbed EGF on their surface at days 3 and 7. Based on these results it was stated that prepared hydrogel has the potential to be used for wound healing application ([Gao et al., 2020](#)). Stabilization of PVA using another primary alcohol, propanol, was proposed by Kenawy et al. ([E.R. Kenawy et al., 2024](#)). In this work, PVA/aloe/caffeine and PVA/aloe/vitamin C membranes were prepared. For this purpose, the solution casting method and the physical approach of PVA chain cross-linking were used. The solutions placed in Petri dishes were immersed in propanol for 8 h, thus obtaining stable, water-insoluble membranes. Propanol allowed the removal of water molecules from the material, facilitating the formation of intermolecular hydrogen bonds in the polymer chains. Effective cross-linking was additionally confirmed by SEM, FT-IR, XRD and TGA analyses. SEM analysis also showed that the addition of aloe vera extract changes the morphology of PVA nanofibers, and additionally, with increasing aloe concentration, the pore size of the hydrogel increases. The membranes showed a high gel content and an increase in the swelling coefficient with increasing aloe content in the material. Importantly, the presence of aloe extract improved the thermal stability of the hydrogels. Aloe vera also had an effect on the increase in the release of caffeine and vitamin C, as well as the adsorption of proteins on the surface, as shown by *in vitro* tests. *In vivo* studies on *Albino* rats showed that the released caffeine and vitamin C reduce inflammation and accelerate wound closure compared to pure PVA membranes and PVA/aloe membranes. The developed systems are, therefore, another potential candidate for use as dressings that accelerate wound healing ([E.R. Kenawy et al., 2024](#)).

Figure 6. "Green" approaches to PVA cross-linking and their effect on hydrogel properties: freeze-thawing, enzymatic reactions, and irradiation. a) Cycles of freezing (ice crystal formation) and thawing (gelation) in the F-T method (top); Properties and applications of the obtained hydrogel (bottom). Reproduced with permission ([Adelnia et al., 2022](#)), Copyright 2022, Elsevier Ltd. b) Enzymatic cross-linking of poly(vinyl alcohol)/silk fibroin semi-interpenetrating hydrogel – generation of tyrosine radicals through horseradish peroxidase activation, followed by gelation in the presence of H_2O_2 (top-left). Gelation time depends on the SF content in the precursor solution (top-right). Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license ([Niu et al., 2019](#)), Copyright 2019, The Royal Society of Chemistry; Scheme of the gelatin-PVA hydrogel synthesis with microbial transglutaminase as a cross-linking agent – mTGase allows the creation of covalent peptide bonds between γ -carboxamide group of a glutamine residue and the ϵ -amino group of a lysine residue in gelatin (bottom). Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license ([CoronaEscalera et al., 2022](#)), Copyright 2022, The Authors. c) Fabrication process of stimuli-responsive N-maleoyl functional chitosan/PVA nanofibrous hydrogel. The MCS/PVA precursor solution was electrospun, and then nanofibers were exposed to UV radiation in the presence of allyl disulfide.

Obtained hydrogel released the encapsulated drug in the presence of a biocompatible reductant. Reproduced with permission ([C.K. Chen & Huang, 2016](#)), Copyright 2016, American Chemical Society. d) Scheme of dually cross-linked PVA/cellulose nanofiber composite hydrogel preparation – chemical cross-linking using a γ^{60} radiation, physical cross-linking by annealing at 80 °C, and rehydration (left). Obtained hydrogel can lift a weight of 1 kg (right). Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license ([Yang Chen et al., 2024](#)), Copyright 2024, The Authors.

4.5 “Green” vs. conventional cross-linking

“Green” approaches in the context of polymer cross-linking are the technological approaches that focus on minimizing the negative impact on the environment during the creation of three-dimensional polymer structures. They include the use of sustainable raw materials while reducing the emission of harmful and toxic chemical compounds. Traditional cross-linking agents, such as glutaraldehyde or boric acid, can be toxic and harmful to both health and the environment. In contrast, “green” cross-linking approaches use safe alternatives that minimize environmental impact. Therefore, they clearly differ from conventional cross-linking as “green” methods must follow specific standards. These include: (I) The use of natural cross-linkers like plant-based and biocompatible substances ([TorresFiguerola et al., 2023](#); [W. Zhang et al., 2023](#)); (II) Physical stabilization through techniques such as irradiation or heat treatment that promotes cross-linking without the need for additional chemicals ([Sau et al., 2021](#)); (III) The use of “green” solvents being biodegradable or derived from renewable resources; (IV) Sustainability, which, in addition to the requirements placed on cross-linking agents and solvents, also requires energy efficiency, minimization of waste and end-of-life considerations. A selection of “green” PVA cross-linking approaches can be found in **Table 1**. The resulting materials are applied across various fields, including agriculture, biomaterials, environmental protection, food packaging, and energy. Nonetheless, it has both benefits and limitations. The benefits and limitations of „green” PVA cross-linking are summarized in **Table 2**.

Table 1. “Green” approaches for PVA cross-linking.

CROSS-LINKING AGENT	APPLICATION	REFERENCE
ALKYL KETENE DIMER	Waterproofing	(Nguyen & Lee, 2022)
HUMIC ACID	Agriculture	(Torres-Figueroa et al., 2023)
TEMPERATURE	Optical and mechanical	(Sau et al., 2021)
CITRIC ACID	Metal extraction and gas adsorption	(Truong et al., 2017)
TARTARIC ACID	Degradable battery separator	(Yuan et al., 2024)
MALEIC ACID	Metal extraction and gas adsorption	(Truong et al., 2017)
POLYACRYLIC ACID	Cartilage tissue, metal extraction, gas adsorption	(Y. Cheng et al., 2020; Truong et al., 2017)
N1, N6-BIS(OXIRAN-2-YLMETHYL) HEXANE-1,6-DIAMINE	Stabilizing electrospun PVA nanofibers	(Y. Zhang et al., 2022)
TANNIC ACID	Food packaging	(W. Zhang et al., 2023)

Table 2. Benefits and limitations of “green” PVA cross-linking.

	BENEFITS	LIMITATIONS
1	<p>Environmental friendliness</p> <p>(It uses safer and biodegradable chemicals that are less harmful to our environment)</p>	<p>Lower cross-linking efficiency</p> <p>(It potentially leads to weaker or less water-resistant materials compared to conventional methods)</p>

2	Biocompatibility (Obtained PVA-based materials are ideal for biomedical applications)	Longer processing time (e.g., the freeze-thawing cycles take days)
3	Sustainability (Reagents are derived from renewable sources)	Variability (Use of natural agents such as citric or tannic acids can potentially cause variability in the final product properties)
4	Mild conditions (Lower energy requirement)	Higher costs (While “green” agents can be more sustainable, their price might be higher than that of conventional chemicals)
5	Enhancement in material properties (It can enhance specific properties, such as strength, flexibility, and thermal stability, without compromising biodegradability)	Difficulties in scaling processes (Industrial implementation of “green” approaches requires technology optimization)

In summary, “green” cross-linking of PVA is advantageous for applications where environmental and health safety is a priority. However, for applications that demand high durability and strong resistance to water or stress, conventional cross-linking may still be preferable unless further advancements are made in “green” cross-linking efficiency. Recently, an increasing number of scientists have been working to address these challenges.

5. APPLICATIONS OF PVA-BASED BIOMATERIALS

5.1 Wound dressings

PVA is commonly used in wound healing dressings because of its hydrophilic properties, biocompatibility, low toxicity, and biodegradability. Developing biocompatible hydrogels with self-healing properties is crucial for effective wound closure, and the high number of hydroxyl groups in PVA allows it to return to its original shape by forming hydrogen bonds between molecular chains. Alifah *et al.* developed a self-healing hydrogel wound dressing composed of PVA and clindamycin,

achieving its sustained release through cross-linking with borax (**Figure 7a**) ([Alifah et al., 2024](#)). This hydrogel significantly enhances wound healing and re-epithelialization in biofilm-infected wounds in mice ([Alifah et al., 2024](#)). In another work, Liu *et al.* presented a self-healing PVA wound dressing combined with β -cyclodextrin and polyethyleneimine (**Figure 7b**) ([D. Liu et al., 2022](#)). This hydrogel showed excellent antibacterial properties, good biocompatibility, exceptional deformability, and self-healing ability, stretching up to 150% in the healed state after damage ([D. Liu et al., 2022](#)).

Aerogel-hydrogel biphasic gels (AHB-gels) show potential as innovative wound dressings, combining the storage and sterilization benefits of aerogels with the moist healing environment of hydrogels ([M. Gong et al., 2023](#)). A recent study by Gong *et al.* explored AHB-gels composed of β -lactoglobulin fibrils (BLGFs) and PVA, demonstrating improved porosity, liquid absorption, and biocompatibility. The study used a repeated freeze-thawing process to induce crystallization of PVA and intermolecular hydrogen bonding between the hydroxyl groups of PVA and the hydrophilic regions of BLGFs. The dressings accelerated wound healing, reduced inflammation, and promoted collagen deposition and neovascularization in animal models. While these findings are promising, several considerations remain. While the dressings support cell proliferation and adhesion, further exploration of their long-term stability and degradation behavior in diverse wound environments would strengthen the case for clinical use. The absence of functionalization, such as antimicrobial properties, leaves room for improvement. This work provides a strong foundation but requires further refinement for widespread application ([M. Gong et al., 2023](#)).

Recently, PVA bio-nanocomposites with natural extracts have been developed with remarkable wound-dressing properties. The incorporation of plant extracts into PVA for wound healing aims to enhance biocompatibility and antibacterial properties, resulting in increased cell proliferation, faster epithelialization, and effective remodeling of the extracellular matrix (ECM) ([Aarthi et al., 2024](#); [Fahimirad et al., 2023](#)). Nemati *et al.* demonstrated the production of PVA nanofibers loaded with ZnONPs and curcumin (Cur) using electrospinning ([Nemati et al., 2025](#)). The Cur/ZnONPs/PVA nano dressing exhibited sustained curcumin release of approximately 19.7% after 8 h and 61.1% after 168 h. This Cur/ZnONPs/PVA combination showed greater antioxidant potential than PVA, ZnONPs, and Cur

alone. The dressing also displayed effective antibacterial properties and led to the greatest increase in wound contraction in rats ([Nemati et al., 2025](#)). Xi et al. conducted a study in which they developed hydrogels by combining Fructus Ligustri Lucidi polysaccharide extracts with poly(vinyl alcohol) and pectin using a freeze-thaw method ([Xi et al., 2024](#)). These hydrogels exhibited outstanding physicochemical properties, including swell ability, water retention, degradability, porosity, drug release, transparency, and adhesive strength, all while maintaining minimal cytotoxicity. Additionally, the hydrogels demonstrated multifunctional features, such as strong antibacterial activity, enhanced re-epithelialization, reduced presence of inflammatory cells, collagen fiber formation, collagen I deposition, and rapid ECM remodeling ([Xi et al., 2024](#)).

5.2 Drug delivery systems

Poly(vinyl alcohol) is a versatile polymer with excellent film and fiber-forming properties, biocompatibility, and biodegradability, making it a promising material for drug delivery systems (DDS). Moreover, the choice of cross-linking method for this polymer gives the possibility to control the swelling behavior, porosity, and mechanical properties of PVA hydrogels, which in turn influence drug release profiles. Mostly explored biomaterials for drug delivery applications, including cross-linked hydrogels, such as those with citric acid ([Fraga et al., 2023](#)) or xanthan gum ([Zang et al., 2022](#)), demonstrate efficient pH-responsive drug release, enabling site-specific and time-dependent delivery. Moreover, electrospun nanofibers were investigated because these systems can provide better control over the release of many drugs ([Zhan et al., 2021](#)). Core-shell and blended nanofibers significantly enhance sustained and localized delivery of hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs ([Kharaghani et al., 2019](#)).

One of the simplest ways to fabricate PVA-based drug delivery systems is by forming them into a hydrogel ([Ghorpade et al., 2019](#)). In the paper by Ghorpade et al., the preparation and characterization of a carboxymethylcellulose/poly(vinyl alcohol) (CMC/PVA) hydrogel loaded with gentamicin sulfate (GTM) was described. CMC/PVA film was specifically engineered to achieve extended drug release for water-soluble basic drugs. Cross-linking was performed using CA as a low-cost, non-toxic cross-linker. Then, the hydrogel was immersed in an aqueous solution of GTM to swell and thereby

incorporate a model drug into the system. Created cross-links helped to hold the GTP molecules in the hydrogel structure via electrostatic interactions and hydrogen bonding. The hydrogel films demonstrated good swelling capacity and hemocompatibility. The release profiles showed a sustained and controlled drug delivery pattern with increasing concentrations of PVA. The hydrogel film with the highest GTP release retardation contained 0.6% w/v PVA, achieving $80 \pm 2\%$ release after 24 h. Films with lower PVA concentrations, such as 0.4%, 0.2%, and 0.1% w/v, exhibited progressively faster drug release, ranging from $86 \pm 2\%$ to $98 \pm 2\%$, respectively, at the same time point. The slower release in the 0.6% w/v PVA film was due to increased intermolecular interactions, which restricted drug diffusion, making this composition optimal for controlled drug delivery ([Ghorpade et al., 2019](#)).

Another study that explored the potential of PVA cross-linked with citric acid was done by Sabzi *et al.* ([Sabzi et al., 2020](#)). The authors integrated PVA with silver nanoparticles for pH-sensitive drug delivery. The hydrogels demonstrated a controlled release of ciprofloxacin, with a higher release rate at pH 7.4 (intestinal conditions) due to ionized carboxyl groups from CA, enabling swelling and drug diffusion. The incorporation of AgNPs reduced the initial burst effect by creating additional cross-linking points, resulting in slower drug release (82% released after around 8 h, compared with 65% for PVA/AgNPs). After around 8 h, the release reached a plateau, and no release was observed. However, the study's evaluation of drug delivery was limited by static testing conditions and a narrow pH range (1.2 and 7.4). The release mechanism was attributed to non-Fickian diffusion, though deeper structural analysis was lacking. The incorporation of CA, AgNPs, and ciprofloxacin into the PVA matrix demonstrated significant antibacterial effectiveness against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* strains. While the system shows potential as an oral drug carrier, enhanced release modeling, enzymatic degradation studies, and broader biological evaluations are needed to establish its clinical applicability ([Sabzi et al., 2020](#)).

The work of Niu *et al.* ([Niu et al., 2019](#)) explores the design, fabrication, and evaluation of enzymatically cross-linked PVA/SF semi-IPN. The study targets hydrophobic drug delivery, using paeonol as the model drug. PVA is both a structural component and an emulsifier for dispersing paeonol in aqueous environments. The authors describe hydrogel characterization in terms of gelation time, morphology,

mechanical properties, swelling, and drug release. The cumulative release profiles of paeonol from the hydrogels at 37 °C in PBS over 48 h showed an initial burst release with cumulative release rates exceeding 50% within the first 12 h. This was followed by a slower, sustained release without a visible plateau, likely due to the gradual dissolution of PVA interpenetrating the SF network through weak molecular interactions. The authors report cumulative releases ranging from 57% to 73%, increasing with greater PVA content in the PVA/SF blend. However, the study lacks kinetic analysis, making it difficult to understand the underlying release mechanisms. They conclude that PVA/SF hydrogels are promising candidates for drug delivery systems, particularly for hydrophobic drugs ([Niu et al., 2019](#)).

Another eco-friendly cross-linker that was used to form PVA-based DDS was o-vanillin (**Figure 7c**) ([Karakurt et al., 2021](#)). It was used with a chitosan-PVA blend for enrofloxacin (ENR) release for transdermal drug delivery. The formulation demonstrated mechanical strength enhancement and controlled drug release, attributed to the cross-linked network restricting polymer mobility. While comprehensive analytical evaluations such as FT-IR, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), and SEM confirmed cross-linking and drug incorporation, the interaction between PVA and ENR remains underexplored. The drug release study showed an initial burst phase followed by sustained diffusion consistent with Fickian behavior. The burst likely results from ENR's surface localization, as indicated by SEM and AFM. The sustained release correlates with the Fickian diffusion mechanism, supported by o-vanillin cross-linking restricting polymer chain mobility. In the non-cross-linked CS-PVA blend, ENR was rapidly released, reaching 50% cumulative release within 3 h. However, o-vanillin cross-linking significantly reduced the release rate to 15–25%, with the 3% w/v o-vanillin-cross-linked film showing the lowest cumulative release after 12 h due to restricted water access and slower drug dissolution. According to the authors, the findings indicate that the material with increased cross-link density could serve as an effective matrix with improved release kinetics for potential local drug delivery applications ([Karakurt et al., 2021](#)).

Another commonly used method for making DDS with controlled release is the development of core-shell nanofibers. Kharaghani *et al.* used PVA as the core material for delivering water-soluble diclofenac sodium salt (DSs) in a wound dressing application ([Kharaghani et al., 2019](#)). As the shell, the

authors used poly(acrylonitrile) (PAN) with another drug – gentamicin (**Figure 7d**). The core-shell structure made with the dipping method ensured relatively uniform PAN coating. High concentrations caused pore blockage, limiting drug release efficiency. Furthermore, DSs showed sustained release over 60 h. The authors dipped the ethanol-cross-linked PVA mat in PAN with different polymer concentrations. However, no dependency was observed in terms of drug release. The gentamicin release from PAN was more rapid than DSs, with 80–90% release after 12 h independently of the PAN concentration. The paper effectively highlights the potential of PVA-based core-shell nanofibers for dual drug delivery. However, the lack of mechanistic explanations, drug release modeling, and bacterial studies limits its clinical applicability ([Kharaghani et al., 2019](#)).

The encapsulation of drugs in poly(vinyl alcohol)/poly(acrylic acid) (PVA/PAA) cross-linked electrospun fibers using emulsion-electrospinning offers a promising approach to enhancing bioavailability and controlled release of hydrophobic bioactive compounds ([Zhan et al., 2021](#)). The authors encapsulated Tangeretin (Tan)—an antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer flavonoid—into this system. The slow-release behavior of thermally cross-linked PVA/PAA/Tan electrospun fibers was characterized by a reduced initial burst and extended-release period compared to pure Tan emulsions. While the Tan emulsion released 37% of its content in the first 5 h and reached full release by 35 h, the electrospun fibers released only 40% in 15 h and took 79 h to reach 80% release. Increasing the PVA/PAA concentration from 6% to 8% reduced the total Tan released within 40 h from 62% to 49%, suggesting that higher polymer concentrations improved retention by creating a denser matrix that slowed diffusion. However, as in previous cases, the release from PVA water-based DDS is relatively fast and finishes after 24 h ([Zhan et al., 2021](#)).

In future scientific endeavors, smart PVA-based systems (e.g., stimuli-responsive hydrogels) will likely dominate next-generation drug delivery technologies. Moreover, integrating advanced manufacturing techniques (e.g., 3D printing) will open new possibilities for customizing drug delivery platforms. In summary, PVA is essential in drug delivery systems, particularly hydrogels and nanofibers for controlled and targeted drug release. Its adaptability ensures its continued relevance in biomedical innovations.

Figure 7. Applications of PVA-based biomaterials. a) Self-healing PVA/borax/clindamycin hydrogel for biofilm-infected wounds. Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license ([Alifah et al., 2024](#)), Copyright 2024, The Authors. b) β -cyclodextrin/polyethyleneimine/PVA hydrogels with improved healing and antibacterial features. Reproduced with permission ([D. Liu et al., 2022](#)), Copyright 2022, Elsevier Ltd. c) Schematic representation of the chitosan-PVA hydrogel film preparation for transdermal drug delivery of enrofloxacin. The solvent casting method was followed by cross-linking with o-vanillin. Reproduced with permission ([Karakurt et al., 2021](#)), Copyright 2021, Elsevier B.V. d) Core-shell nanofiber for dual simultaneous delivery of gentamicin and diclofenac sodium salt. Reproduced under CC BY 4.0 license ([Kharaghani et al., 2019](#)), Copyright 2019, The Authors.

5.3 Tissue engineering

PVA's ability to form hydrogels, scaffolds, and nanofibers through various fabrication methods such as electrospinning, freeze-thaw techniques, and 3D printing makes it highly versatile in addressing the

diverse needs of tissue engineering applications. Additionally, these fabrication techniques allow for the creation of various architectures—ranging from porous scaffolds to nanofiber mats and hydrogel films—that can mimic specific tissues' structural and functional properties. This versatility is crucial for developing constructs tailored to the unique requirements of skin, bone, cartilage, cardiac muscle, and other tissue types.

The PVA-based hydrogel system developed by Xiang *et al.* represents a promising advancement in bone tissue engineering ([Xiang et al., 2024](#)). By incorporating tannic acid (TA), hydroxyapatite (HA), and collagen type I (Col-I) into a physically cross-linked PVA matrix, the hydrogel addresses key challenges of traditional PVA, including limited mechanical strength and low bioactivity. Hydrogen bonds between PVA and TA provided improved mechanical properties. HA addition aimed to enhance the compressive strength of the construct and to imitate the inorganic components of natural bone tissue. Improved biocompatibility and bioactivity were achieved through the addition of Col-I. *In vitro* tests using MC3T3-E1 cells highlighted the hydrogel's ability to promote cell adhesion, proliferation, and differentiation, evidenced by increased ALP activity and calcium deposition. The hydrogel effectively mimicked an ECM-like environment, facilitating osteogenesis. Further *In vivo* studies demonstrated the material's ability to regenerate bone and integrate with host tissue in a rat femoral defect model (**Figure 8a**). These findings underscore the potential of this multifunctional hydrogel for bone regeneration, advancing the application of PVA-based materials in tissue engineering ([Xiang et al., 2024](#)).

Xu *et al.* proposed a “green” non-solvent induced phase separation (NIPS) approach to prepare poly(vinyl alcohol)/chitosan cryogels for non-compressible hemostasis (**Figure 8b**) ([Xu et al., 2025](#)). The study explores the synergy of PVA's mechanical properties and CS's hydrophilic and adhesive characteristics. The PVA/CS cryogels demonstrate rapid expansion, excellent mechanical properties, and biocompatibility, attributed to chitosan's regulated hydrogen bonding and dynamic crystallization of PVA molecules. The resulting material showcases a uniform porous structure (70–75 μm) with high tensile strength (0.69 ± 0.04 MPa) and compressive strength (0.32 ± 0.04 MPa), suitable for sealing wounds under pressure. However, its relevance to tissue engineering lies in its scaffold-like properties,

particularly for load-bearing tissues. Despite these merits, the study lacks data on cellular responses, long-term biostability, and controlled biodegradation. While the cryogel rapid swelling and resilience promise temporary hemostasis, broader tissue regeneration applications remain underexplored, warranting further investigation ([Xu et al., 2025](#)).

Bi and co-workers developed a robust chitosan-poly(vinyl alcohol) double-network (DN) hydrogel using a simple freezing-thawing process for tissue engineering applications ([Bi et al., 2020](#)). This hydrogel leverages multiple hydrogen bonding interactions between a rigid chitosan network and a flexible PVA network to achieve high mechanical performance, including compressive stress (60–230 kPa), tensile strain (152–360%), and excellent fatigue resistance (90% recoverability after 5 cycles). Biocompatibility was validated *in vitro* with L929 fibroblasts and rBMSCs, showing over 80% relative proliferation rates, and *in vivo* through rat subcutaneous implantation, which demonstrated accelerated wound healing and reduced scar formation. However, the swelling rate increased significantly with higher PVA content (e.g., weight change: 2% for pure chitosan vs. 154% for pure PVA), potentially limiting applications requiring dimensional stability. The study provides a scalable, eco-friendly alternative for biomedical hydrogels with potential in cartilage and soft tissue repair, yet further investigation into long-term stability is essential ([Bi et al., 2020](#)).

Another study developed hybrid nanofiber scaffolds composed of PVA and 58S bioglass (58SiO₂-33CaO-9P₂O₅) to investigate their potential in cardiac tissue engineering ([RiveraTorres et al., 2024](#)). The scaffolds were fabricated with varying bioglass concentrations (5–30%) using electrospinning and cross-linked with glutaraldehyde to enhance water resistance and thermal stability. Morphological analysis revealed a uniform distribution of bioglass nanoparticles and increasing fiber diameters with higher bioglass content (130–340 nm). Cardiomyocytes seeded on scaffolds with 20–30% bioglass exhibited improved adhesion and synchronous contractile activity due to the controlled release of Ca²⁺ ions, critical for cellular functions. Fluorescence imaging confirmed uniform electrical pulses, leading to synchronized contractions. However, the study only evaluated scaffold stability over 48 h, limiting understanding of their long-term performance *in vivo*. The results suggest that PVA/bioglass scaffolds can promote cardiomyocyte adhesion and function, presenting a promising approach for myocardial

regeneration. Still, future studies should assess their degradation kinetics and efficacy over extended periods ([RiveraTorres et al., 2024](#)).

PVA/Pec composite hydrogels, created by combining poly(vinyl alcohol) and pectin (Pec), offer an innovative solution for bone tissue engineering ([Hu et al., 2022](#)). These hydrogels leverage a dual-network system: a semi-crystalline PVA primary network formed through freeze-thaw cyclic cross-linking and an ionic pectin-calcium secondary network. The ionic “egg-box” structure of pectin facilitates calcium-mediated cross-linking, enhancing structural integrity and immobilizing bioactive components. This dual cross-linking strategy significantly improves mechanical properties such as tensile strength (118 ± 9 kPa) and compressive strength (79 ± 21 kPa) while maintaining high water content and porosity. Biological testing showed improved osteoblast adhesion, proliferation, and osteogenesis, particularly with the PVA/Pec-10 formulation (10% w/v Pec content in the precursor solution), which resulted in a 375% increase in alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity compared to PVA-only hydrogels. The system also promoted bone regeneration *in vivo*, with a 53% increase in bone volume at 8 weeks. However, while promising, long-term clinical data and scalability challenges warrant further investigation ([Hu et al., 2022](#)).

PVA's adaptability in tissue engineering stems from its biocompatibility, tunable mechanical properties, and versatility in forming hydrogels, scaffolds, and nanofibers. Innovations like hybridization with bioactive materials (e.g., bioglass, pectin) and advanced cross-linking techniques enhance structural stability, bioactivity, and osteointegration, effectively addressing challenges in regenerating skin, bone, cartilage, cardiac, and soft tissues.

5.4 Biological filters

Using membrane-based materials for air filtration is a widespread and effective way against air pollution. Traditionally, the preparation of these membranes involves organic solvents, which can cause secondary environmental pollution. However, there is a growing emphasis on creating eco-friendly and safe solutions. This trend is especially noticeable in developing biological filters, that use sustainable materials and processes to effectively remove pollutants. These innovations not only

lessen environmental impact but also provide safer alternatives to conventional filtration methods, reducing reliance on organic solvents and minimizing secondary pollution. PVA is commonly used in biological filters due to its hydrophilicity, biocompatibility, mechanical strength, film-forming ability, and cost-effectiveness, making it an ideal material for effectively removing pollutants. Incorporating various ingredients into PVA, such as pig manure compost ([Chan & Zheng, 2005](#)) and synthetic or natural polymers like chitosan ([S. Wu et al., 2023](#)), is designed to enhance filtration efficiency and sustainability. The PVA additives can boost moisture retention, compressive strength, and buffering capacity, ensuring optimal pH levels and biological activity for effective biofiltration. Zhu *et al.* presented a user-friendly, multifunctional, bio-based air filtration membrane made from chitosan and PVA using “green” electrospinning and UV curing techniques ([M. Zhu et al., 2019](#)). This environmentally friendly method avoids hazardous organic solvents, which can leave harmful residues. To enhance filtration efficiency, superhydrophobic silica nanoparticles were added to the nanofibers to create a rough surface. Additionally, silver nanoparticles were formed on the surface through the UV reduction of AgNO₃, providing antibacterial properties. The CS/PVA@SiO₂/AgNPs membranes demonstrated excellent filtration performance alongside effective antibacterial activity ([M. Zhu et al., 2019](#)). Cui *et al.* presented an environmentally friendly PVA/tannic acid composite nanofiber membrane filter made using “green” electrospinning (**Figure 8c**) ([Cui et al., 2021](#)). The membrane achieved a 99.5% filtration efficiency for PM_{1.0} with a low-pressure drop of 35 Pa ([Cui et al., 2021](#)). Additionally, nanofiber membranes are suitable for face mask applications due to their ability to remove particulate matter while maintaining effective air permeability. An interesting example of a face mask is tannic acid-enriched PVA nanofibrous membranes, which demonstrated excellent UV-shielding (UV-A: 95.7%, UV-B: 100%), antibacterial activity, high particle filtration efficiency (97.7% for PM_{0.6}) with a low-pressure drop (**Figure 8d**) ([S. Y. Lee et al., 2023](#)).

Figure 8. Applications of PVA-based biomaterials. a) Scheme of the fabrication and application of physically cross-linked poly(vinyl alcohol)/hydroxyapatite/tannic acid/collagen type I (PVA/HA/TA/Col-I) hydrogel. Developed hydrogel proved to be effective in the treatment of femoral defects *in vivo*. Reproduced with permission (Xiang *et al.*, 2024), Copyright 2024, Elsevier B.V. b) Poly(vinyl alcohol)/chitosan (PVA/CS) cryogel structure and its properties. Material is a potential candidate for use in non-compressible hemostasis. Reproduced with permission (Xu *et al.*, 2025), Copyright 2025, Elsevier B.V. c) PVA/tannic acid nanofiber membrane enhances air filtration. Reproduced with permission (Cui *et al.*, 2021), Copyright 2021, Elsevier Inc. d) Tannic acid-enriched PVA membrane for UV and antibacterial protection in masks. Reproduced with permission (S. Y. Lee *et al.*, 2023), Copyright 2023, American Chemical Society.

5.5 Biosensors

Poly(vinyl alcohol) is widely used in biosensors due to its excellent film-forming capability and ability to cross-link with various agents, enhancing enzyme immobilization and sensor performance.

Ismail *et al.* demonstrated a potentiometric biosensor utilizing penicillinase immobilized in a chemically cross-linked PVA matrix with bovine serum albumin (BSA) ([Ismail & Adeloju, 2014](#)). The cross-linking was achieved by mixing specific concentrations of PVA and BSA with penicillinase, forming a film through air drying. Optimization of components, including 2.5% w/v PVA and 0.006% w/v BSA, was critical to achieve high sensitivity (linear detection range of 7.5–283 mM) and a detection limit of 1.7 mM for penicillin. The mild cross-linking conditions preserved enzyme activity while creating a permeable and stable matrix for effective biosensing in pharmaceutical and food matrices ([Ismail & Adeloju, 2014](#)).

Devi *et al.* explored the fabrication of conductive hydrogels based on a cross-linked blend of PVA and polyaniline (PANI), focusing on the tunability of gel properties and electrical conductivity by varying the PANI-to-PVA ratio ([Devi et al., 2024](#)). The hydrogel formation relied on the interpenetration of PANI and PVA matrices, as evidenced by FT-IR spectra showing changes in the –OH group signals, indicative of interactions between the two polymers. The hydrogels exhibited composition-dependent swelling behavior and electrical conductivity. Current-voltage measurements validated the material suitability as a conductive matrix. These properties were optimized for dual applications: as electrode materials for supercapacitors, achieving cyclic stability of ~95% after 1000 cycles, and as an enzymatic glucose biosensor with an impressive LOD of ~0.001 μM . The study underscored the potential of PVA/PANI conductive hydrogels as multifunctional platforms for energy storage and biosensing applications, further enhancing the scope of PVA-based materials in high-performance and biomedical technologies ([Devi et al., 2024](#)).

Naghieb *et al.* extended PVA application to electrochemical biosensing by synthesizing a PVA/graphene oxide (GO)/AgNPs nanocomposite, where PVA provided biocompatibility, GO enhanced surface area and electron transfer, and silver nanoparticles boosted conductivity ([Naghieb et al., 2018](#)). The fabrication process involved a solution-based method that ensured uniform distribution of GO and AgNPs within the PVA matrix. SEM analysis revealed a rough and porous structure, which increased the contact area between the enzyme layer and the composite, enhancing electrocatalytic activity. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy confirmed a significant reduction in charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), indicating improved conductivity. The resulting glucose biosensor exhibited a broad linear range (150

nM to 10 mM), high sensitivity ($15.32 \text{ mA M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), and a low detection limit (25 nM), making it highly suitable for clinical diagnostics ([Naghib et al., 2018](#)).

Idris *et al.* utilized gamma irradiation to cross-link PVA in the fabrication of a glucose biosensor based on a tapered optical fiber, where PVA blended with pyrrole (Py) created an environment that effectively immobilized glucose oxidase (GOx) ([Idris et al., 2018](#)). This approach resulted in a robust matrix with enhanced enzyme adhesion, as evidenced by FT-IR, XPS, and surface morphology studies. The irradiated Py/PVA-GOx films exhibited a significant increase in thickness and surface roughness, indicative of successful cross-linking and enzyme entrapment. The Michaelis-Menten constant (K_m) for the irradiated films ($5.99 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mM}$) was substantially lower than that of non-irradiated ones ($2.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mM}$), demonstrating improved catalytic activity and stronger enzyme-matrix interaction. The linearity and sensitivity of the biosensor were also critically influenced by the cross-linking process. The irradiated biosensor showed a two-phase linear response to glucose concentrations, with sensitivity rates of $8.7 \times 10^{-3} \text{ } \mu\text{W mM}^{-1}$ and $0.1152 \text{ } \mu\text{W mM}^{-1}$ across concentration ranges of 0.001–1.0 mM and 1.0–20.0 mM, respectively. Compared to non-irradiated fibers, the irradiated matrix displayed stable enzyme immobilization, reduced enzyme leaching, and higher response rates at higher glucose concentrations due to robust cross-linking and covalent bonding between the polymers and enzyme. The strong adhesion prevented the enzyme from detaching under physiological conditions, ensuring reliable biosensing performance ([Idris et al., 2018](#)).

Similarly, Coşkuner Filiz *et al.* fabricated cross-linked CS/PVA nanofibers using electrospinning to develop a naked-eye colorimetric glucose biosensor ([Coşkuner Filiz et al., 2021](#)). The nanofibers were cross-linked to improve mechanical stability while retaining high biocompatibility. Cross-linking facilitated the effective immobilization of GOx and HRP, resulting in a functional biosensor that detected glucose concentrations through a visible color change, highlighting the potential for point-of-care applications. These strips demonstrated a color change proportional to glucose concentration, from white (0 mM) to brownish (13.8 mM), and a detection range from 2.7 to 13.8 mM ([Coşkuner Filiz et al., 2021](#)).

Thus, the use of nanostructured PVA-based matrices has shown advantages in biosensing. For example, PVA integration with nanomaterials, such as PVA/GO composites or PVA-based nanofibers, provides improved mass transfer, enhanced enzyme loading, and superior mechanical stability. These features support robust and durable biosensors with high sensitivity and selectivity. The adaptability of cross-linked PVA across different sensor modalities—potentiometric, electrochemical, optical, and colorimetric—highlights its role in providing a stable and biocompatible environment for enzymes, improving mass transfer, enhancing electron conductivity, and enabling highly sensitive and selective biosensing platforms.

6. FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

PVA is a synthetic, water-soluble polymer primarily derived from the hydrolysis of poly(vinyl acetate) and characterized by its excellent biocompatibility, hydrophilicity, and biodegradability ([Vatanpour et al., 2023](#); [M. Yang et al., 2023](#)). These properties, combined with its chemical versatility, make it highly suitable for a wide range of applications, including biomedical, environmental, and packaging industries. Currently, the global PVA market is witnessing robust growth, with its market size valued at approximately USD 1.2 billion in 2024, and is projected to reach USD 1.8 billion during 2025-2033 ([Polyvinyl Alcohol Market Overview, Size & Report | 2033, 2025](#)). This expansion is driven by several factors, including technological innovations, a supportive regulatory environment, and a strong sustainability drive, particularly in food packaging where biodegradability and moisture barrier properties are valued. However, to fully realize PVA's potential as a sustainable material, challenges related to its processing and functionality must be addressed, especially concerning cross-linking methods.

Conventional chemical cross-linkers, like glutaraldehyde though effective, present environmental and health concerns, including potential toxicity or neurological and developmental effects ([Oh et al., 2022](#); [Zeiger et al., 2005](#)). While glutaraldehyde typically biodegrades under aerobic conditions, its widespread use necessitates careful handling ([Leung, 2001](#)), underscoring the urgent need for safer, more sustainable alternatives.

Developing eco-friendly materials aligns with the evolving paradigm of “green” chemistry, emphasizing processes that minimize environmental impact while meeting industrial needs. This shift reflects the aims of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 12, which promotes responsible consumption and production ([Anastas et al., 2021; Goal 12 | Department of Economic and Social Affairs](#)). In the context of PVA, “green” cross-linking approaches favor bio-based agents, renewable resources, and eco-friendly solvents that enhance biodegradability and reduce reliance on hazardous chemicals. However, any shift toward new PVA cross-linking agents must be approached with caution to avoid unintended consequences, such as the emergence of new pollutants. Emerging pollutants refer to substances not traditionally monitored or regulated that gain widespread use and production, eventually accumulating in ecosystems where they can exert unanticipated and harmful effects on human health and the environment ([X. Liu et al., 2024; Picinini-Zambelli et al., 2024](#)). Environmental impact assessments and lifecycle analyses will be crucial to ensure that new alternatives align with long-term sustainability goals without unintended ecological burdens. While promising, adopting cross-linking agents from organic wastes and bio-based sources introduces its own challenges such as the need for additional purification steps that could, increase production cost and energy use. One way to address this challenge is to advocate minimal intervention when adopting functional agents from organic or bio-derived sources ([Zargarian et al., 2024](#)). Avoiding intensive purification methods like pyrolysis could mitigate this, striking a balance between sustainability and efficiency.

Among PVA processing techniques, electrospinning stands out as a powerful method for producing nanostructured PVA hydrogels ([Zakrzewska et al., 2023, 2025](#)). Electrospun fibers form networks with high surface area and porosity, ideal for biomedical applications. Cross-linking these nanostructures significantly enhances mechanical strength and functionality. However, nanostructured PVA introduces a dual-faceted dynamic in its interaction with water molecules as it exhibits high water susceptibility before cross-linking and increased swelling ratio post-cross-linking ([Zargarian et al., 2025](#)). This heightened swelling capacity is particularly advantageous for applications requiring substantial water uptake, such as drug delivery systems and tissue engineering scaffolds. On the other hand, this increased accessibility introduces critical challenges related to dissolution of non-cross-

linked polymer before cross-linking as well as complications in achieving effective stabilization or retaining the miniaturized geometry in the presence of water. Addressing these challenges involves strategies like pre-incorporating cross-linkers before miniaturization and using water-free cross-linking methods, such as thermal or photo-initiated approaches.

Future strategies for sustainable PVA cross-linking include: (I) Enzyme-mediated cross-linking, where enzymes like laccase or tyrosinase can be utilized to form biocompatible and biodegradable networks by introducing suitable reactive groups into the PVA backbone or by employing enzyme-compatible cross-linkers. (II) Irradiation combined with dynamic covalent chemistry by using agents such as disulfide, imine, or boronic ester to create self-healing or stimuli-responsive PVA-based hydrogels. (III) Use of “green” solvents like ethanol to reduce moisture content and act as cross-linkers ([Lopes & Simoneau, 2014](#); [Zakrzewska et al., 2023](#)). (IV) Application of organic waste-derived agents, such as oxidized pectin from citrus peels, mimicking glutaraldehyde cross-linking pathway due to the presence of dialdehyde groups ([Haj Romdhane et al., 2020](#)). (V) Simple bio-sourced agents, such as lemon juice, which can induce cross-linking in PVA through an esterification reaction ([Zakrzewska et al., 2025](#)). (VI) Adoption of multifunctional sustainable agents, including metal-organic frameworks (MOFs), to impart additional properties (e.g., UV resistance, antibacterial activity, or photothermal effect). While many of these approaches are already in experimental stages for PVA, their optimization and adaptation for specific biomedical and environmental applications remain an important area for future research.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This review provides a comprehensive analysis of state-of-the-art cross-linking methodologies for PVA, emphasizing both physical and chemical approaches while highlighting the transition towards sustainable, environmentally friendly techniques. Physical methods, including the freeze-thaw cycle (benefiting from PVA's inherent ability to form crystallites) and irradiation (utilizing high-energy sources such as gamma rays) were extensively discussed. In the context of chemical approaches, the review examined conventional cross-linking agents alongside innovative “green” alternatives, such as natural cross-linkers derived from bio-sources (e.g., lemon juice) and enzymatic reactions promoting

biocompatibility and biodegradability. Heat treatments and alcohol-based solvents were also explored, emphasizing their potential to minimize water dependency in processing.

The applications of nanostructured, cross-linked PVA materials were showcased across diverse fields, focusing on its versatility and utility. In wound dressings, PVA hydrogel's high swelling capacity and biocompatibility promote effective healing; In drug delivery systems, PVA enables controlled release mechanisms; In tissue engineering, it serves as a scaffold mimicking the ECM; In biological filtration, its structural features facilitate efficient separation processes; In biosensors, PVA's environmental responsiveness supports precise detection capabilities. Collectively, these findings emphasize the transformative potential of PVA in driving advancements in biomedical and environmental technologies, positioning it as a cornerstone material in sustainable innovation.

Funding Information

This work was supported by the National Science Centre (NCN) SONATA BIS Project No. 2020/38/E/ST5/00456 and the Polish National Agency for Academic Exchange (NAWA) under Bekker NAWA Programme, grant number: BPN/BEK/2021/1/00161. S.S.Z. acknowledges the financial support from HORIZON TMA MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships – European Fellowships (HORIZON-TMA-MSCA-PF-EF) action program under the call MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships 2021 (HORIZON-MSCA-2021-PF-01), grant agreement No. 101068036, "SuSCoFilter". F.P. would like to acknowledge the support from The Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO)'s Manufacturing Research Unit in Australia for his temporary visiting position in the Functional Materials team. F.P. and P.N. acknowledge the financial support from the Polish Ministry of Science and Higher Education.

Acknowledgments

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